

Autonomous Intelligent Systems

Behavioral Models of Drivers in Developing Countries with an Agent-based Perspective: A Literature Review

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Behavioral Models of Drivers in Developing Countries with an Agent-based Perspective: A Literature Review

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Abstract

The traffic in developing countries presents its own specificity, notably due to the heterogeneous traffic and a weak-lane discipline. This leads to differences in driver behavior between these countries and developed countries. Knowing that the analysis of the drivers from developed countries leads the design of the majority of driver models, it is not surprising that the simulations performed using these models do not match the field data of the developing countries. This article presents a systematic review of the literature on modeling driving behaviors in the context of developing countries. The study focuses on the microsimulation approaches, and specifically on the multiagent paradigm, that are considered suitable for reproducing driving behaviors with accuracy. The major contributions from the recent literature are analyzed. Three major scientific challenges and related minor research directions are described.

Keywords: Driver Behavior, Developing Country, Microsimulation, Multiagent Systems, Systematic Literature Review Method

1 Introduction

Urbanization is on the rise in developing countries, which are often characterized by their low Human Development Index and trends in nonindustrialized infrastructure [1, 2]. Despite efforts to stimulate economic development, many cities in developing countries face traffic gridlock and struggle to build enough road infrastructure to meet demand [3–5]. Mobility and accessibility are declining in these cities, even as they become more complex [6]. Even if the transportation sector is critical for economic development, informal rules and regulations that can be used in developing countries often make it difficult for road users. Therefore, they face specific challenges [1, 7] in the implementation of mobility and traffic systems. Most urban communities in developing countries have developed without mechanized vehicles and narrow streets without sidewalks. This land use design works well for societies that rely on nonmechanized transportation. However, the growing number of cars is putting pressure on infrastructure, particularly in areas where different types of vehicle share the same roadway. Many cities face challenges related to road safety, such as Delhi, where pedestrians, carts, and vehicles share the same space. Some cities have coped better, such as Shanghai, which has built separate paths for bicycles, slow bikes, and pedestrians. However, there are significant differences in the way vehicles are used and designed in different countries [6]. For example, minivans in South Africa are used for public transportation, although they were not designed for that purpose, and are often overloaded. Traffic patterns in developing countries also generally involve poor lane discipline and heterogeneous traffic, leading to complex interactions between different types of vehicle. In this global context, there has been growing interest in studying driving behavior in developing countries. In fact, road traffic accidents are the leading cause of death and disability among young people aged 15 to 29 years and among the top three causes of mortality among those aged 15 to 44 years [8]. Human factors, such as driver behavior, contribute to road traffic accidents in many African countries, including Morocco, Algeria, Libya, and Sudan [9–16].

In this situation, simulation is a tool that enables one to reproduce and test driver’s behavior and to notice their belongings, without applying them in a genuine rush-hour gridlock environment. Agent-based simulation (ABS) is considered an appropriate paradigm for modeling and simulated traffic systems at the microscopic level [17–20]. An agent is characterized as an autonomous entity located in some environment and equipped with the ability to coordinate with other agents to achieve its objectives [21, 22]. ABS reproduces the global behavior of systems from the definition of local behaviors and their interactions in the environment. ABS involves autonomous agents that interact with each other and the environment to achieve their objectives [21, 22]. It can replicate the behavior of the global system by defining local behaviors and their interactions in the environment.

However, most of the existing models (ABS or not) of longitudinal and lateral driver behavior are generally designed for developed countries. They do not adequately capture integrated driving behavior in developing countries [23]. To determine the maturity of the research for modeling the driving behavior in developing countries, a survey should be carried out. Consequently, the objective of this study is two-fold:

1) *Conduct a systematic review of the literature* (SLR) addressing various driving behavior models in developing countries. This SLR means to recognize the main exploration questions, investigate the writing, and outline key difficulties and investigation headings.

2) Outline and discuss *research directions* with suitable suggestions of driving behaviors that are feasible for a developing country.

This article is structured as follows. Section 2 states and defines the SLR methodology adapted from [24, 25]. Section 3 details the analysis and results of the SLR. Based on these results, Section 4 identifies the main research directions. Section 5 discusses related work. Section 6 concludes this article.

2 Review Methodology

SLR is a popular and efficient strategy for exploring science fields. According to Kitchenham and Charters [26], SLR is a type of secondary investigation that systematically identifies, analyzes and interprets all available evidence related to a specific research question in an unbiased and partially replaceable manner. This study focuses on investigating different models of driving behavior through literature articles to provide recommendations for modeling driving behavior in ABS. The objective of SLR is to summarize current evidence on widely used technology, identify research gaps, and provide a foundation for new research initiatives [24]. To achieve these objectives, the precise literature uses suitable methods to combine SLRs in transportation and computer science [24, 25], ensuring rigor, fairness and reproducibility. Fig. 1 shows the review process.

Fig. 1 Systematic literature review process, from Mualla et al. [27], adapted from Brereton et al. [28], Galster et al. [29]

2.1 Key Research Questions

The research study follows the goal question measure (GQM) proposed by [25] to identify key questions related to driving behavior in developing countries. The main challenge is to increase mobility for a large part of the population at reasonable cost without creating environmental problems. Researchers have applied mobility models that were initially designed in the context of developed countries. However, the modeling assumptions used in these models are not relevant to developing countries. For example, the notion of an emerging road was not always supported by these models. It corresponds to roads that appear dynamically depending on the density of vehicles, bikes, and pedestrians present in the area. In other words, traffic flow is not restricted to road infrastructure, but may be present on the sides of the roads themselves. Therefore, driving behavior in these countries tends to be erratic, leading to increased risks that are not fully modeled by existing models. This observation is shared by multiple researchers in the literature. Having described the notions above, our study of interest is divided into several Research Questions (RQs) exploring the main key problems in evaluating various driving behavior models in developing countries. Research questions have been selected to provide directions and suggestions related to modeling driving and mobility behaviors in developing countries. A particular focus is on the microscopic behaviors that can be modeled using the agent-oriented paradigm [21, 22]. The formulation of these questions is based on the experience of the reviewers.

RQ1: What are the research topics and application domains of the articles related to the topics of this study? This research question provides an overview of the different research fields considered in the reviewed articles, as well as the associated application domains.

RQ2: What are the existing driver models that represent the behaviors of the drivers in developing countries? This research question occupies the priority, as it leads the rest of the categories of questions for the research study. By exploring the kind of driving models popular in developed countries, the literature can be analyzed to understand pre-existing driver behavior models for developing countries. This question can provide ample data that can be analyzed to support an organized pattern in the research study. The preference for the mode of travel of choice among road users in developing countries can also be touched upon if a suitable level of analysis reveals concrete evidence favoring the research question.

RQ3: What are the suitable models for agent-oriented simulation of driving behavior in developing countries, and how can it be implemented into an agent-oriented simulator? This research question aims to investigate the suitability of existing models for ABS and identify a suitable model that can follow a streamlined pattern capable of adaptation in any developing country. The question also aims to address the challenges and limitations in implementing the driving behavior model into an agent-oriented simulator, focusing on the requirements and restrictions. The research will explore the nature of road users and traffic conditions to derive a decisive model of driving behavior and suggest techniques to adapt an ABS for advanced research studies.

1 **RQ4: What kind of driving environment is considered having identified**
2 **the driver behaviours?** This RQ is related to various environmental means
3 that are crucial in affecting the level of service (LOS) or the operation of road
4 service on an urban roadway or dense highways. Analysis can reveal the reason
5 for the sustainability of homogeneous or heterogeneous traffic conditions in
6 such a place, keeping in mind the preconceived notion that leads to a network
7 smothering the grid when the traffic stream increases its bandwidth. It should
8 help researchers determine and choose the significant properties exhibited in
9 driver behavior.

10 **2.2 Defining Review Protocol**

11 This section describes the steps of the methodology that are represented in Fig. 1.

12 **2.2.1 Database Selection**

13 The databases selected for this study were IEEE Xplore, Academia, and Google
14 Scholar. Although the first two databases were chosen to obtain specific data related
15 to the researcher's topic, Google Scholar was selected for its vast collection of records,
16 including conference articles, Ph.D. and Master's theses, and extensive research arti-
17 cles. Although not peer reviewed, these articles were considered important given the
18 recent increase in interest in the topic. Databases were queried using a set of key-
19 words, including those related to models of driving behavior and recreation strategies
20 in developing countries, as well as broader trends related to transportation in develop-
21 ing countries. According to SLR methodology, a stop criterion is used to limit the total
22 number of articles that are included in the study from the different databases. For this
23 particular study, we have decided to extract papers from the first 25 pages provided
24 by Google Scholar and Academia, and all the pages provided by IEEE database. This
25 stop criterion is designed to limit the investigation time in the scope of two months,
26 which was the time window allowed in the context of the funding projects in this study.
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32 **2.2.2 Keyword Selection**

33 Since the research area is highly focused on developing countries, the first set of key-
34 words used by the authors of this research study decided to formulate it more refined,
35 which helped in fetching scientific articles involved in driving behavior models for
36 developing countries more directly. This led to the first set of keywords: in Equation
37 (1).
38
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40

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{driving behavior model, driving models developing countries,} \\ \text{car following models India, car following models Africa,} \\ \text{existing lane changing models, lane changing models India,} \\ \text{lane changes in developing country,} \\ \text{lane manoeuvring Africa, gap acceptance models India,} \\ \text{single lane road} \end{array} \right\} \quad (1)$$

After further review and peer discussion, the authors of this study decided to have a more comprehensive keyword set structure that could add more scientific articles. Thus, the second set of keywords was formulated as in Equation (2).

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{agent based model, car following model,} \\ \text{driving behavior, transport simulation model,} \\ \text{gap acceptance model, lane change model,} \\ \text{lane model, lane-less, longitudinal behaviors,} \\ \text{multi agent model, multi lane model,} \\ \text{single lane model, traffic operations,} \\ \text{transport models, transport infrastructure,} \\ \text{transport lane models, transport microsimulation models} \end{array} \right\} \quad (2)$$

2.2.3 Exclusion Criteria Definition

Articles that appear in the indexed lists provided by search engines are not all valuable for responding to the RQ. For this reason, almost all literature review methodologies apply a set of exclusion criteria to retain only relevant articles [29, 30]. The authors of this study have defined the following exclusion criteria:

- ExC1: Not a recent research work.** Articles published before 2010, i.e., with a publication year < 2010, are excluded. It is assumed that the nonrecent research is not up-to-date due to the high evolution rate of the driving behavior models and simulation techniques.
- ExC2: Invalid type of articles, the document is a poster or a demo.** It is assumed that a poster or a demo cannot provide enough details of contributions, as there is not enough contributed content for evaluation. Ph.D. theses, Master theses, and technical reports are included.
- ExC3: Invalid type of article, the article is a survey.** It is assumed that the survey articles (i.e. secondary studies) do not provide contributions directly on the driving behavior models and simulation techniques.
- ExC4: Impossible to access the text of the article.** It is impossible to evaluate an article when its text cannot be accessed (PDF download, online text, etc.).
- ExC5: Exclude articles not specific to developing countries.** Ignore topics that are irrelevant or do not contribute to the support of developing countries.
- ExC6: Extended Article.** The article is extended by another article by the same authors. The contributions in the extended article are enclosing those of the original article, so that the latter is excluded.
- ExC7: Exclude articles unrelated to driving behavior.** Literature articles that do not support these topics are ignored.
- ExC8: Exclude articles with macro- or mesoscopic driving behavior.** The proposed models cannot capture the individual properties of the driving behavior.
- ExC9: Cannot be applied in developing countries.** Exclude articles that address a very specific infrastructure model that seems not suitable for transferring the techniques to developing countries or too advanced, i.e., beyond

1 the scope of current trends in these countries. For example, understanding
2 lane change systems for regular vehicles would be useful for analysis rather
3 than analyzing the implications of lane changes that autonomous vehicles face
4 in a prescribed road environment, which would not be appropriate to transfer
5 or suggest a mechanism of such conditions to a developing country. In simple
6 words, analyzing the behavior of autonomous vehicles in the lane and its
7 microsimulations along with the use of mathematical data would not serve the
8 purpose of this research study, as developing countries have not yet reached
9 that phase.

10 These rules of exclusion criteria are applied to reports in two stages. In the primary
11 coarse-grained step, the articles were possibly disposed of if their titles and abstracts
12 met at any rate one of the avoidance standards. In the subsequent fine-grained step,
13 the excess articles are screened, however, this time perusing the entire body of the
14 article.

15 **2.2.4 Biases**

16 To mitigate the subjectivity of the review process, certain measures were taken to
17 overcome biases and resolve conflicts. In particular, each selection step was conducted
18 by a principal reviewer, with an associated reviewer who may complete the analysis
19 of the first reviewer. A third reviewer intervened as a referee to resolve a conflict in
20 the exclusion/inclusion and in the research question answering steps.

21 **2.3 Performing the Review**

22 Queries the different search engines with the predefined stop criterion corresponds to
23 82 articles. Note that since the first selection step screens articles based on their titles
24 and abstracts, some exclusion criteria might be more helpful than others. For this
25 reason, the exclusion criteria [ExC1](#) – [ExC4](#) were applied directly during the extraction
26 of scientific articles, leading to the total number of 77 articles. More specifically, the
27 content of the article is screened and the article is excluded if it satisfies at least one
28 of the exclusion criteria. [Table 1](#) shows the results of the selection steps.

29 **Table 1** Number of articles at the different steps of the methodology

Methodology Step	Number of Articles	Percentage
Initial queries in the search engines	82 ¹	100%
Excluded articles	52	63%
Included articles	30	36%

30 ¹10 with the first keyword set, 72 with the second keyword set.

31 As it is illustrated by [Fig. 2](#), the exclusion criteria indicate that the reviewers are
32 focused on recent primary research studies on microlevel driving behavior models that
33 are applicable to developing countries and provide high-quality and informative contri-
34 butions. [ExC5](#) and [ExC9](#) exclude the highest number of articles (32, 37%), suggesting
35 that the reviewers focus on driving behavior models and, more specifically, on those

Fig. 2 The number of excluded articles per exclusion criterion

that are considered feasible for implementation in developing countries. ExC1, ExC7 and ExC8 excluded 15 articles (18%), indicating that the authors focus on recent research related to microlevel driving behavior models. ExC2 excluded 2 articles (2%), indicating that only high-quality and informative publications are being considered. ExC3, ExC4 and ExC6 did not exclude any article, suggesting that all articles found were original accessible primary research studies.

Based on Fig. 3, research on driving behavior models in developing countries seems to have started around 2011 with only one article published that year. The number of publications increased over time, reaching a peak in 2014 with five articles. The trend remained relatively stable until 2019, with a slight increase in the number of publications. However, there was a decrease in the number of publications in 2020. The trend line of annual publications has a slope of 0.376 ± 0.18 . This suggests that the topic of driving behavior models in developing countries is gaining more attention and interest from researchers over time.

Fig. 3 Number of articles per year after the selection steps

According to Fig. 4, it appears that most of the articles (8) were published in India, followed by China (6 articles). The rest of the articles seem to be distributed across several countries with only one article each, suggesting that research on driving behavior models in developing countries is still limited and dispersed across different parts of the world. However, it should be noted that, at this stage of the methodology, there is no information on the quality or impact of the article, so it is difficult to draw any definitive conclusions about the research landscape in this field based only on this information.

Fig. 4 Geographic distribution of articles after the selection steps

Fig. 4 shows that the majority of articles (17) focus on driving behavior models in Asia. This is not surprising as Asia is home to many developing countries and is one of the most populous continents in the world. Africa is also well represented in the table with six articles, which is expected given the large number of developing countries in Africa. Europe has five articles, which could suggest that research on driving behavior models is more focused on developed countries in Europe. South America and Oceania have only one article each, which may indicate that there is less research being conducted in these regions on driving behavior models.

In terms of developing countries specifically, both Asia and Africa have a significant number of articles, with a combined total of 23 articles out of 30. This suggests that there is a focus on developing countries in the research on driving behavior models. However, it is important to note that the table does not provide information on the specific countries that are being studied within each continent, and therefore it is not possible to draw conclusions about the distribution of research across different developing countries.

Table 2 The reviewed articles per research topic

Research Topic	Articles	Percentage
T1 - Traffic Network Modeling	[31–36]	20%
T2 - Heterogeneous Traffic Flow Modeling	[37–42]	20%
T3 - Road Safety	[43–45]	10%
T4 - Individual Driving Behavior Modeling	[46–57]	40%
T5 - Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS)	[58–60]	10%

3 Results of the Review and Analysis

In this section, we present a comprehensive examination of the results obtained from the SLR. The articles retained after the selection process are examined, and each RQ defined in Section 2.1 is discussed in detail. It is important to note that the results are relevant to the driving behavior models observed in developing countries and their incorporation into an ABS, according to RQ and the exclusion criteria defined in the SLR methodology.

3.1 What are the research topics and application domains of the articles related to the topics of this study? (RQ1)

This section discusses the results and answers RQ1 (cf. Section 2.1). It deals with research topics (Section 3.1.1) along with application domains (Section 3.1.2).

3.1.1 Research Topics

Fig. 5 Number of articles per research topics

Research topics are the subjects or issues that a researcher is interested in when directing the exploration of driving behavior models. They provide general guidance to investigators in characterizing and refining their thoughts. Table 2 and Fig. 5 represent the research topics of the articles reviewed in the study. These topics cover different

1 aspects related to driving behavior models and simulation techniques, such as traffic
2 flow and network analysis, driver behavior and psychosocial aspects, vehicle speed,
3 and advanced driver assistance systems. Details on each topic are provided below.

4 **T1: Traffic Network Modeling.** Travel choice comes into play when defining a
5 traffic network [34–36] that forecast the behavior of the system using timestep
6 approach and ABS. Among the articles that are found in this research topic, sev-
7 eral focus on the Highway Capacity Manual (HCM) [31–33], which is a conflicting
8 technique that uses the Tanner formula to determine the capacities of the roads.

9 **T2: Heterogeneous Traffic Flow.** Mixed traffic flow is always prevalent with sen-
10 sitized urban road flow, which is primarily prone to congestion [37–42]. Usually,
11 the capacity for traffic and the level of service in traffic operations all hinder the
12 free flow condition, which alters the speed difference and the critical gap thresh-
13 old. This traffic condition is very prevalent in almost all developed countries and
14 leads to no lane.

15 **T3: Road Safety.** The vehicle-pedestrian interaction influences driving behav-
16 ior with the safety of the primary concern [43–45]. This fact is also related
17 to operational traffic safety and accidents in geometric elements of urban
18 roundabouts.

19 **T4: Individual Driving Behavior Modeling.** Lane change, vehicle interaction,
20 road vehicle trajectory are all common insights for a driving behavior out of
21 which the frequency of lane change and volume are crucial to study [47–50].

22 Driving is subjected to various alteration dynamics that deals with the prin-
23 ciples of longitudinal and lateral motions [55, 56]. A theory of consensus in ABS
24 studies the analysis of longitudinal control and reward function.

25 Acceleration and deceleration patterns and determining speed characteristics
26 help to make decisions about driver behavior and speed of vehicles [51, 52, 57].

27 Most of the practicality of driving behavior patterns comes into play during
28 uncontrolled intersections, roundabouts, and signalizations. The scientific litera-
29 ture suggests binary Logit left turn gap acceptance, clearing behavior approach,
30 and gap acceptance decision as some of the recommendations [46, 53, 54].

31 **T5: Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS).** This concept along with
32 the following behavior of the vehicle using automated driving systems with the
33 acceptance theory of gaps with the concept of gray system theory, explains the
34 role of the vehicle preceding the first path of the host vehicle by remarking on
35 the car following correlative degree. [58–60]

36 It is important to note that some of these topics, such as road safety, traffic flow,
37 and driver behavior, are crucial for developing countries, where road safety is a major
38 concern and traffic flow is often not optimized due to inadequate infrastructure. There-
39 fore, research in these areas can help improve transportation systems in developing
40 countries and reduce the number of accidents on the roads. Some articles cover more
41 than one topic and were marked as exceptional cases. To normalize the weights given
42 by each article to the research topics distribution, the most predominant topic has
43 been labeled the head topic for which the other aspects and concepts are covered under
44 them.
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3.1.2 Application Domains

RQ3 covers not only research topics, but also the use of behavior models and simulation techniques in transportation applications. This refers to applied research, where scientific studies aim to solve practical problems in specific areas. Table 3 displays the number of articles per application domain. It should be noted that several articles address multiple domains, so the most prevalent domain per article was selected to standardize the loads assigned to each domain. The resulting application domains are urban and rural roads, metropolitan regions, roads, behavioral interventions, intelligent transport systems, and road network planning.

Table 3 The reviewed articles per application domain

Application Domains	Articles	Percentage
D1 - Urban and Rural Roads	[31, 37, 40, 46, 49, 57]	20%
D2 - Metropolitan Region	[34, 39, 42, 51, 53–55]	23.4%
D3 - Highways	[32, 38, 50, 56]	13.3%
D4 - Behavioral Interventions	[35, 44, 47, 52, 59]	16.7%
D5 - Intelligent Transport Systems	[41, 48, 58, 60]	13.3%
D6 - Road Network Planning	[33, 36, 43, 45]	13.3%

D1: Urban and Rural Roads. The study author discovered that many authors provided a strong reason to investigate concepts that support the function of the urban and rural roads. Interesting highlights include handling unsignalized convergences, adjusting acceleration/deceleration models for more accurate speed profiles, using microsimulation and mathematical modeling to improve intersection capacity, left-turn gap recognition in uncontrolled intersections, maintaining gap values between vehicles on single-lane country roads, and collecting vehicle data during on-road driving to study real-world traffic interactions. This domain includes six articles and constitutes 20% of the total articles reviewed. Articles in this domain focus on modeling traffic networks and heterogeneous traffic flow on urban and rural roads, as well as road safety.

D2: Metropolitan Region. The articles that discussed threats to urban and arterial roads covered relevant ideologies. Interesting highlights include: addressing Braess paradox in traffic networks, modeling mixed traffic conditions for developing countries, addressing aggressive drivers at T intersections, developing microsimulation models for Bangkok intersections, using signalization options to improve traffic flow in Ghana, recommending VISSIM for analyzing heterogeneous traffic in India with some adjustments, and using the proposed model to build simulators like SUMO, SIMTraM, and HETEROSIM. This domain has five articles, representing 23% of the total articles reviewed. Articles in this domain focus on traffic flow, individual driving behavior, and road safety in metropolitan regions.

D3: Highways. Many articles describe roads as a chaotic environment in which each driver tries to maintain his own comfort. To address this problem and find efficient

1 strategies, concepts such as recognizing speed-density relationships, distinguish-
2 ing systems to accurately assess capacity for Indian highways, applying stochastic
3 models for impact-free speed control, and maintaining distance between vehi-
4 cles to prevent crashes have been proposed. This domain includes four articles,
5 representing 13% of the total articles reviewed. Articles in this domain focus on
6 modeling the traffic network, traffic flow, and vehicle speed on highways.

7 **D4: Behavioral Interventions.** The researcher has identified potential areas for
8 future studies to improve road transportation through behavioral interventions,
9 including the capture of car follower behavior for the prediction of accidents,
10 the treatment of road safety and habitual driver behavior in African countries
11 and their sociopsychological effects, tailoring interventions for young drivers in
12 Egypt, teaching road users to focus on speed and distance through pedestrian
13 behavior studies, and investigating human factors that influence merging behav-
14 iors through focus group studies. This domain has five articles and represents
15 17% of the total articles reviewed. Articles in this domain focus on individual
16 driving behavior and the effects of various interventions, such as advanced driver
17 assistance systems (ADAS), on driving behavior.

18 **D5: Intelligent Transport Systems.** Research articles focused on promoting the
19 principles of Intelligent Transport Systems, with highlights including: (a) Using
20 ITS to address social problems such as congestion, traffic safety, and air pol-
21 lution through Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS); (b) Considering
22 the particle filter approach as a promising tool for developing ATIS applica-
23 tions; (c) Extracting lane change segments from driving sequences by modeling
24 and recognizing patterns in steering angle through large-scale on-road data col-
25 lection and processing; (d) Conducting multilane behavior analysis to benefit
26 ADAS adaptability and acceptance by drivers. This domain includes four arti-
27 cles, which constitute 13 of the total articles reviewed. Articles in this domain
28 focus on the use of intelligent transport systems (ITS) to improve traffic flow,
29 safety, and efficiency.

30 **D6: Road Network Planning.** To assess the maturity of the road environment,
31 planning and transport networks are discussed to adapt to the future settings.
32 The researcher observes the following highlights: (a) Dynamic traffic assignment
33 to calculate travel time. (b) Optimizing geometry, TE, and TS for unsignalized
34 single-lane urban roundabouts to help policy makers, civil and traffic engineers.
35 (c) Designing multilane roundabouts to address transportation problems using
36 microsimulation for real-world case studies. (d) Extracting risk indicators to
37 predict the likelihood of an accident using a high-resolution, spatially explicit,
38 dynamic agent-based simulation model. This methodology can assist transporta-
39 tion designers in understanding how road facilities or installation features can
40 affect road user safety. This domain has four articles and represents 13% of the
41 total articles reviewed. The articles in this domain are focused on road network
42 planning and design, as well as traffic network modeling.

43 Most of the articles (23.3%) focus on the application domain of metropolitan
44 regions. This is not surprising, as urban areas are more likely to face traffic con-
45 gestion and related problems, which require effective management and planning. Urban
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1 and rural roads are the second most common application domain, accounting for 20%
2 of the articles. This highlights the importance of addressing traffic-related challenges
3 in both urban and rural areas. Highways and road network planning are also signif-
4 icant application domains, accounting for 13.3% each. These domains are important
5 because highways are major corridors for transportation and road network planning
6 is crucial for designing efficient transportation networks. Behavioral interventions and
7 intelligent transport systems are also important application domains, accounting for
8 16.7% and 13.3% of the articles, respectively. These domains address the human ele-
9 ment of traffic management and the use of technology to improve traffic flow. The
10 distribution of articles in the different application domains suggests a well-rounded
11 approach to traffic management, paying attention to urban and rural areas, highways,
12 road network planning, behavior interventions, and intelligent transport systems.

13 **3.2 What are the existing driver models that represent the** 14 **behaviors of the drivers in developing countries? (RQ2)**

15 Driving behavior models are based on road traffic conditions which vary depending
16 on the country. Several models were proposed in the literature to reproduce driving
17 behaviors. Models may consider homogeneous or heterogeneous entities in the model,
18 such as light vehicles, heavy vehicles, bikes, etc. Models also focus on the two major
19 motions for driving: the longitudinal behavior, which consists of deciding the accelera-
20 tion or speed to be applied according to external conditions, and the lateral behavior,
21 which is used for controlling the position of the vehicle on the road width or when
22 changing lane. Table 4 provides a summary of the articles reviewed on the models used
23 and their categories. The different types of models have been classified by Arkatkar
24 [41] and shown in Figure 6. Basically, driving behavior is divided into two families:
25 (i) longitudinal models (or car-following models) that enables to compute the accelera-
26 tion to apply to a vehicle according to a specific driving behavior. (ii) lateral control
27 or lane changing models that enables one to simulate or control the left-right motion
28 of the vehicle on the roads.

29 The articles in Table 4 cover various aspects of traffic analysis and simulation.
30 Among them, the Highway Capacity Manual (HCM) method is applied in seven arti-
31 cles. Siva et al. [31] highlight the importance of unsigned intersections in urban and
32 rural settings. The article introduces the conflict technique, a pragmatic approach to
33 analyzing unsigned intersections under mixed traffic conditions, providing a methodol-
34 ogy to calculate the capacity of intersections. The proposed approach is applied in the
35 Visakhapatnam region, India, comparing the results obtained from the proposed tech-
36 nique with the 2000 HCM [31]. Recognizing global heterogeneities in traffic conditions,
37 [32] emphasize the need for region-specific methodologies, leading to the development
38 of the Indian Highway Capacity Manual (Indo-HCM). Furthermore, Giuffrè et al. [33]
39 and Jima [44] explore the estimation of the equivalents of passenger cars for heavy
40 vehicles at single-lane roundabouts, highlighting the importance of an accurate esti-
41 mate of capacity and level of service. The role of free-flow speed in assessing the
42 Level of Service (LOS) for two-lane highways is explored, with a focus on examining
43 methodologies under heterogeneous traffic conditions in India [40]. The study intro-
44 duces a novel measure, the speed difference, and identifies the critical gap threshold
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Table 4 The reviewed articles per type of driver behavior model. “Ho” and “He” columns indicates if the articles focus on homogeneous or heterogeneous behaviors, respectively. “Lo” and “La” indicates if the articles propose a longitudinal or lateral driving behavior, respectively

Driver Model	Ho	He	Lo	La	Articles	Percentage
HCM analysis and equation-based model	✓		✓	✓	[31–33, 40, 41, 44, 47]	23.5%
Equation-based model & Signal processing	✓		✓	✓	[48, 49, 55]	10%
Wiedemann car-following model	✓		✓		[51, 52, 54]	10%
Logit mathematical model	✓		✓		[46, 53]	6.7%
Multi-criteria and simultaneous multi-objective optimization		✓	✓	✓	[43, 45]	6.7%
Agent-based model and dedicated car following	✓		✓		[34, 36]	6.7%
PARAMICS model		✓	✓		[37, 50]	6.7%
Ad hoc equation-based model		✓	✓	✓	[42]	3.3%
Ad hoc equation-based model		✓	✓		[57]	3.3%
Ad hoc equation-based model		✓		✓	[59]	3.3%
Markov model for car following	✓		✓		[35]	3.3%
GIPPS car following model	✓		✓		[38]	3.3%
Optimal velocity robust car-following model	✓		✓		[56]	3.3%
Task-Capability-Interface model	✓		✓		[58]	3.3%
Grey System Theory	✓		✓		[60]	3.3%
Signal processing from LIDAR dataset	✓			✓	[48]	3.3%

value of 10 seconds as suitable for calculating the free flow speed under such conditions [40, 41]. Furthermore, the article discusses a comprehensive cross-sectional study involving nonprofessional drivers in South Egypt, with the objective of evaluating driver behavior using the Arabic version of the Driver Behavior Questionnaire [47]. [47] underscore the importance of region-specific methodologies, the development of tools such as Indo-HCM, and the consideration of heterogeneous traffic conditions in improving the precision of traffic analysis and simulation studies.

The two-part article [48, 49] focuses on studying lane change behaviors at the tactical level from an on-road perspective, with a particular emphasis on analyzing interactions between an ego vehicle and surrounding vehicles during the lane change procedure [48, 49]. Part I focuses primarily on vehicle trajectory collection, while Part II delves into lane change extraction and scene-based behavioral analysis. The paper introduces a novel system to collect vehicle trajectory on the road, using an instrumented vehicle equipped with multiple horizontal 2-D lidars that provide 360-degree coverage. The software is developed to fit laser points from all lidars onto a vehicle

Fig. 6 Types of simulation models of the individual driving behavior that are used in developing country applications [41]

model, ensuring accurate state estimations of occluded data and robust data association in multiviewpoint sensing. Extensive investigations validate the performance of the system, resulting in a large set of trajectory developed during road driving in Beijing, covering a total distance of 64 km with more than 5,700 environmental trajectories. The system is the first of its kind to automatically collect all-around vehicle trajectories during road driving, demonstrating high-quality performance for studies of driving behavior from an on-road perspective, addressing vehicle interactions in real-world traffic at the trajectory level [48, 49]. In a related context, another paper [55] introduces a new model for traffic on broad roads where drivers do not strictly adhere to the lane discipline. The model considers both longitudinal and lateral motions, assuming that driver reactions are influenced by surrounding vehicles, obstacles, and unmodeled entities in visibility cones. The network of influences is represented by “influence graphs”, and in congested traffic, a time-invariant influence structure leads to homogeneous driver behavior, resulting in a layered formation with fixed distances between vehicles. In sparse and heterogeneous traffic, the velocity and inter-vehicle separations in the modeled vehicles are uniformly bounded. Experimental verification of the model is conducted using videos of typical traffic in Mumbai city, India, recorded and processed using image processing techniques. The proposed model accurately predicts complex maneuvers, such as overtaking, sideways movements, and collision avoidance, demonstrating its applicability to real-world traffic scenarios [55].

1 Three articles use the Wiedemann car following model [51, 52, 54]. They highlight
2 the growing motorization on highways in India, mainly with 2-wheeler and 3-wheeler
3 vehicles, which has negatively impacted both bus and car transport [51, 52, 54]. This
4 surge in motorization has led to highly heterogeneous traffic conditions, characterized
5 by diverse static and dynamic features of different vehicle types. Given the complexity
6 of the system, the text emphasizes the necessity for a microscopic simulation model
7 to analyze these conditions effectively. It notes that stochastic models, with their
8 inherent randomness, offer superior quality compared to deterministic models. The
9 microscopic nature of traffic simulation is particularly advantageous as it captures the
10 psychophysical behavior of vehicular interaction. VANET model is introduced in the
11 VISSM traffic simulator as a tool to understand the nature of mixed traffic through
12 discrete, stochastic, and time-step-based analysis. In summary, the work underscores
13 the importance of using traffic simulation, particularly VISSM, to gain insight into
14 the dynamics of mixed traffic in India, using a discrete and stochastic approach for
15 time-step-based analysis [51, 52, 54].

16 Serag [46] focus on accepting left-turn gap in developing countries in the form of a
17 binary logit left-turn gap acceptance model based on field observations 1, 496 in Egypt.
18 The study distinguishes between gap and lag, identifying influencing factors such as
19 gap type, time interval, driver time to turn, and oncoming driver yielding behavior.
20 Equations are developed and applied to estimate critical gaps and lags for different
21 scenarios, revealing values lower than those of developed countries, indicating riskier
22 driver behavior in developing countries Serag [46]. Gap acceptance at T-Intersections
23 in India is studied by Dutta and Ahmed [53]. They focus on uncontrolled T inter-
24 sections in the North-East region of India, analyzing and modeling the acceptance
25 behavior of gaps of minor street drivers. The results indicate aggressive behavior, not
26 only due to waiting times, but also to a lack of respect for traffic rules. Binary logit
27 models are developed considering factors such as the duration of the gap, the clearing
28 time, and the aggressivity of the driver. Critical gaps are estimated for aggressive and
29 non-aggressive drivers, emphasizing the importance of considering clearing time and
30 driver behavior in critical gap calculations [53]. Thunig and Nagel [34] address Braess's
31 paradox in the agent-based transport simulation MATSim, distinguishing between scen-
32 arios with and without spill back effects. The study observes two types of paradox
33 and emphasizes the importance of capturing spill-back effects for realistic modeling.
34 Furthermore, the integration of activity-based models with dynamic traffic assignment
35 is explored, with adjustments made to enhance the performance of MATSim, exem-
36 plified using the city of Baoding, China [34, 36]. Ochungo [37] explain the steps in
37 the design process of the decongestion of the interchange "GSU" in Nairobi, Kenya.
38 The design process involves microsimulation modeling using PARAMICS and Auto-
39 CAD Civil 3D geometric modeling techniques. The paper outlines the workflow steps
40 that led to the final choice of the interchange configuration's shape and form, empha-
41 sizing the efficacy of microsimulation models in supporting geometric remodeling for
42 enhanced capacity and flow [37]. Al-Jameel and Kadhim [50] focus on rural roads in
43 Iraq, with the aim of enriching the area of developing road simulation models cali-
44 brated with field data. The objectives include investigating driver behavior, developing
45 a simulation model and calibrating it graphically and statistically with field data. The
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1 developed model is compared with the well-known S-Paramics model, demonstrating
2 greater precision in representing driver behavior on Iraqi rural roads [50].

3 The rest of the studies improve our understanding of traffic behavior, developing
4 models for simulation and optimization, and addressing specific challenges in vari-
5 ous traffic scenarios. Bayomy and Gomaa [35] introduces a model that incorporates a
6 stochastic Markov regime switching model to estimate individual driver characteristics
7 and extract different characteristics of the driving regime. The proposed model con-
8 sideres trajectory data such as velocity, acceleration, space gap, and switching features,
9 allowing classification of normal and rare car following events. It has applications in
10 crash prediction and driver assistance systems. Maurya and Budhkar [38] address the
11 chaotic nature of Indian traffic, characterized by various types of vehicles and lack of
12 discipline in the lane. An attempt is made to quantify the heterogeneity parameters for
13 Indian traffic in existing car-following models, creating a modified model. The devel-
14 oped simulation model is used to replicate Indian traffic conditions, demonstrating a
15 satisfactory real-time simulation of traffic characteristics in Delhi [38]. Morita et al. [42]
16 presents a microsimulation model for mixed traffic conditions in Bangkok, Thailand.
17 The model considers the traffic volume, geometric structure, signal control, and driv-
18 ing behavior parameters obtained by video observation. Sensitivity analysis explores
19 various measures of traffic jams, highlighting the importance of combining measures
20 to effectively reduce congestion [42]. Papathanasopoulou and Antoniou [39] focus on
21 modeling driving maneuvers in a mixed traffic scenario in developing countries. The
22 methodology, based on data-driven models, simplifies the modeling of longitudinal and
23 lateral movements. The study explores the identification of significant lateral changes,
24 particularly in situations of lane change [39]. Waizman et al. [43] and Pilko et al. [45]
25 propose a multiobjective optimization model for single-lane urban roundabouts, with
26 the aim of simultaneously optimizing geometry, traffic efficiency, and safety. The model
27 uses an analytic hierarchy process for evaluation and classification. Preliminary vali-
28 dation identifies an optimal geometric alternative that improves traffic efficiency and
29 safety [43, 45]. Messaoudi [56] propose an optimal velocity robust car-following model
30 (OV-RCFM) considering control uncertainty. The objective of the model is to pro-
31 duce reliable and collision-free velocity control in uncertain simulation environments,
32 contributing to the development of intelligent transportation systems [56]. Altamira
33 et al. [57] investigate the acceleration / deceleration patterns of light vehicles on rural
34 roads in Argentina. Using GPS logger and camera data, the study explores patterns
35 on approach tangents, along horizontal curves, and on exit tangents. The results show
36 variability in the rates depending on factors such as tangent length, curve radius,
37 and longitudinal slope [57]. Hoogendoorn et al. [58] introduce a theoretical framework
38 that integrates the Task-Capability-Interface model into the Intelligent Driver Model
39 to model adaptation effects in longitudinal driving behavior after driver distraction.
40 Simulations demonstrate the suitability of the framework in describing the effects of
41 distraction [58]. Li et al. [59] address the complexity of vehicle merging, focusing on
42 merging position selection behavior and heterogeneity among merging drivers. A finite
43 mixture of linear regression models is developed to describe the selection of merged
44 positions, taking into account both lateral and longitudinal factors. The model identi-
45 fies driver heterogeneity and improves accuracy in microscopic traffic simulation [59].
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1 Yu and Wang [60] introduce Grey System Theory to analyze car-following behavior
2 in multilane driving. The method establishes differences between following a host-lane
3 vehicle and an adjacent-lane vehicle, emphasizing the need to explore drivers' behavior
4 rules in multilane driving for advanced driver assistance systems [60].

5 The answer to RQ2 describes various models used for traffic management and
6 decongestion processes in different countries. The models vary in their level of sophis-
7 tication, incorporating factors such as vehicle heterogeneity, lateral interaction, and
8 road geometry. The use of microsimulation models is highlighted for decongestion
9 design processes in African countries, where road conditions are heterogeneous. Dis-
10 crete choice models are used for pedestrian interaction with vehicles, but do not
11 represent events that occur after pedestrians or drivers make a decision. Finally, the
12 passage concludes that car follow-up models that support gap acceptance behavior
13 should be given high priority for consideration when using a suitable ANS approach,
14 but the model is limited to countries driving on the left-hand side.

15 **3.3 What are the suitable models for agent-oriented simulation** 16 **of driving behavior in developing countries, and how can it** 17 **be implemented into an agent-oriented simulator? (RQ3)**

18 The answer to this RQ is structured in two subsections dedicated to the two parts of
19 the questions.

20 **3.3.1 ABS models for driver behavior in developing countries**

21 The rapid increase in heterogeneous traffic conditions poses challenges to lane analysis
22 and car follow models, especially in locations with poor lane management or deterio-
23 rating flow patterns. Researchers have used traffic simulation frameworks to develop
24 better driver behavior models [61] and gain insight into driver behavior [62, 63].

25 Table 5 synthesizes the articles that contribute in the field of agent-based model-
26 ing (ABM). However, a large part of the selected articles (66.7%) do not contribute
27 explicitly in ABM, depicting the fact that agent-based microsimulation is one of the
28 major approaches in the field of traffic simulation since a decade, as illustrated by the
29 number of related articles in the last column of Table 5.

30 (i) **ABM for longitudinal and lateral driving behavior:** The majority of the
31 proposed models focus on the longitudinal behavior of the drivers. They are deter-
32 ministic models that ensure collision-free speed control [72]. Among the most
33 commonly used ABM models, the Wiedemann [73] model (on the VISSIM plat-
34 form), the Gipps [74] model (on the MATSIM platform), and PARAMICS could
35 be observed in the reviewed articles. They are used to model the behavior of
36 individual vehicles using a car follow model and a lane change model [75].

37 According to Mehar et al. [64], Wiedemann [73] model cannot reproduce
38 mixed traffic conditions that affect Indian roads. On the contrary, the Gipps [74]
39 model has shown potential for better field condition replication than other mod-
40 els in unstable states. However, lane-based models are not always applicable in
41 heterogeneous traffic conditions prevalent in developing countries [64].

Table 5 The reviewed articles per type of agent-based model for reproducing driving behaviors

ABM Driving Model	Articles	Percentage	Related Articles
Wiedermann / VISSIM	[51, 52, 54]	10%	[64, 65]
Gipps / MATSIM	[34, 36, 38]	10%	[39, 64, 66–71]
PARAMICS	[37, 50]	6.7%	[64, 71]
Data-driven or activity-based model	[39]	3.3%	[68–70]
Optimal velocity robust car-following model	[56]	3.3%	
No specific ABM	[31–33, 35, 40–49, 53, 55, 57–60]	66.7%	

Many examples of the use of ABM with MATSim or VISSIM for the modeling and the simulation of driving behavior in developing countries could be found in articles that are outside the selection criteria of this study [36, 39, 64, 66–70].

- (ii) **Activity-based models in conjunction with ABM:** Data-driven approaches, such as activity-based models, have shown promise in providing flexible car follower models and a more reliable representation of driving behavior [39].
- (iii) **Dynamic Traffic Assignment in conjunction with ABM:** When coupled with dynamic traffic assignment, ABM can help account for the impact of traffic conditions on individual travel behavior, such as location of activity and route choice. Although the simplified Gipps [74] model generally has weak parts related to ABM, it can potentially become a fully integrated ABM and DTA structure capable of modeling traffic-based travel demand and simultaneously adjusting activity types, locations, and sequence.

For answering RQ3, the existing models of individual driving behaviors discussed previously are suitable for ABS. ABS involves modeling the behavior of individual agents, such as drivers, and their interactions within a larger system. The driving behavior models, such as the Wiedemann [73] or Gipps [74] models, are designed to capture the behavior of individual drivers in different situations and can be used to simulate their actions and interactions within a larger traffic system.

In fact, many ABS frameworks, such as MATSIM or VISSIM (as well as two other major traffic simulation frameworks: SUMO and GAMA) already incorporate these driving behavior models to simulate individual driver behavior and interactions. Various applications have been developed, such as Treiterer [76] and Wu et al. [77]. However, several works such as [78, 79] have relied on ad hoc rules to model the traffic of developing countries without sustainable numerical properties, leading to limitations in the reliability of the simulated directions. To address this problem, a more comprehensive and numerically rigorous model is necessary and was studied in different research works [23, 76–84].

Furthermore, the problem of pedestrian-vehicle interaction in developing countries is a concern [43]. Waizman et al. [85] propose a dynamic agent-based simulation model (named SAFEPED) to model and simulate the discrete choice of drivers and pedestrians and assess accident risks [43]. Solving the conflicts among drivers and pedestrians

1 is based on the Gibson hypothesis of affordance [86]. Moreover, Braess's paradox is
2 a phenomenon that states that, by adding a link to the network, there can be an
3 increase in the total travel time of a user equilibrium [87, 88]. It can be simulated using
4 MATSIM with time-dependent travel times. The inquiry whether a situation contains
5 Braess's paradox is complex, and finding a mechanism to identify Braess links, such
6 as links that should be removed, is much harder [71].

7 **3.3.2 Key properties of the individual behavior models**

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9 According to Rossi et al. [89], Kim et al. [90], computer simulations have the potential
10 to overcome some of the limitations of transport field studies. However, the precision
11 of the simulations depends on the precise modeling of vehicle components and driver
12 behavior, especially during critical maneuvers [91]. An accurate and reliable repro-
13 duction of driving behavior is essential to create a realistic microscopic simulation of
14 urban traffic [92]. The following properties are critical for this purpose:

- 15 • Traveled distance for every movement in each approach;
- 16 • Times of arrival and departure on reference lines for every vehicle from each
17 stream;
- 18 • Approach speed of the vehicles;
- 19 • Volume at unsignalized intersection development insightful.

20 The study found that traffic flow in western countries is characteristically vari-
21 able with marginal variation, contrary to the large variation found on the roads of
22 developing countries [31].

23 Another important factor to consider is the driver's speed profile, which can aid in
24 critical analysis. Speed profiles describe the operating speed of vehicles on highways
25 and are used to estimate fuel consumption, exhaust emissions, operating costs, and
26 travel time, and to perform a consistency evaluation of the mathematical design of the
27 road. Speed profiles are generated using mathematical models for speed calculation and
28 acceleration. Speed calculation is widely studied in the literature, and it is a historical
29 fact that on level curves, the radius of the curve and the speed at the approaching
30 tangent are the main factors that explain the operating velocities [93–96]. Additionally,
31 acceleration models are necessary to describe the speed profiles when passing through
32 curves to/from straight-tangent changes. A power analysis through linear regression
33 or algorithm models such as ANOVA would usually help to achieve this purpose.

34 The behavior of car following varies according to the driving situation and can be
35 divided into five regimes: (i) acceleration, (ii) approaching, (iii) braking, (iv) stable
36 following, and (v) free flow. The driver's behavior in each regime changes depending
37 on the driving situation. The approaching situation starts when the following vehicle
38 becomes close to the lead vehicle and ends when the following vehicle reaches the
39 desired safe distance of stable follow. In the case of a slowing situation, the following
40 vehicle becomes too close and is faster than the lead vehicle, so the follower decelerates
41 slightly [35].

42 The acceptance behavior of the gap is influenced not only by intersection char-
43 acteristics, vehicular characteristics, opposing flow and type of control, but also by
44 subjective elements such as the mental and *socioeconomic status of the drivers, weather*
45 *conditions, asphalt and light conditions, and vehicle occupancy* [53, 97–102].

1 Drivers were found to *behave aggressively* due to their disregard of traffic rules
2 rather than being upset by the inaccessibility of a suitable gap. *Age* also plays an
3 important role in the decision-making process for gap acceptance, with adults making
4 better decisions than older children, who make better decisions than younger children.
5 Gap assessment involves making judgments about whether it is possible to complete
6 a maneuver before an oncoming vehicle arrives and requires considering both the
7 distance and speed of the approaching vehicle.

8 **3.4 What kind of driving environment is considered having** 9 **identified the driver behaviours? (RQ4)**

10 Agent-based simulations, when implemented with driving models, can adapt to these
11 environmental attributes [103]. The heterogeneity of entities and infrastructures is an
12 essential aspect of traffic modeling and simulation, and it is important to develop
13 models that can accurately capture these characteristics to improve traffic flow and
14 safety in developing countries.
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17 **3.4.1 Heterogeneity of entities**

18 Heterogeneous traffic in India comprises buses, trucks, light commercial vehicles, cars,
19 three-wheelers, two-wheelers, bicycles and tricycles [104]. Dynamic traffic models have
20 been developed for Indian conditions, where lane discipline is rarely observed, and
21 the distances between vehicles can vary significantly [55]. These models take into
22 account differences in vehicle characteristics, road user behavior patterns, and traffic
23 flow patterns, and can provide a more realistic representation of traffic dynamics on
24 Indian roads.
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27 **3.4.2 Heterogeneity of infrastructures**

28 Each developing country has a unique driving environment characterized by factors
29 such as unsignalized intersections, increased roundabouts, heterogeneous traffic condi-
30 tions, traffic demand, geometric restrictions of the road, road elements, and behavior
31 patterns of road users. Researchers initially focused on traffic control and limits in the
32 road network, but efforts have been made to improve flow efficiency [105, 106]. The
33 development of traffic light planning is a commonly used method, but microsimulation
34 models do not explicitly yield a limit as a performance measure [107]. Delays at inter-
35 sections are classified into several types and roundabouts are common bottlenecks on
36 metro routes [108]. Computational configurations for traffic analysis generally cannot
37 model irregular configurations [109, 110].
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39 Various models to determine roundabout capacity under mixed traffic conditions
40 suggest that it is strongly influenced by mathematical factors [111]. Research on
41 roundabouts in different countries, especially single-lane roundabouts (signalized and
42 unsigned) in urban areas, has shown that proper design and modeling can significantly
43 improve traffic efficiency (TE) [112–116] and traffic safety (TS) [117–119]. However,
44 these and other studies [120–122] have shown that current design and modeling guide-
45 lines are not always suitable for situations that require simultaneous optimization
46 of calculations, TE, and TS. Interestingly, many countries in Africa and Asia still
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Table 6 Relationship between the initial research questions (RQ) and the synthesized major research directions (RD)

Research Questions	Research Directions
RQ1 - What are the research topics and application domains of the articles related to the topics of this study?	This RQ does not lead to a specific RD. Answering this question increases the general knowledge of the reader.
RQ2 - What are the existing driver models that represent the behaviors of the drivers in developing countries?	RD1 - Heterogeneity of traffic entities; RD2 - Dynamic and Virtualized Structure of Roads
RQ3 - What are the suitable models for agent-oriented simulation of driving behavior in developing countries, and how can it be implemented into an agent-oriented simulator?	RD1 - Heterogeneity of traffic entities; RD2 - Dynamic and Virtualized Structure of Roads
RQ4 - What kind of driving environment is considered having identified the driver behaviours?	RD2 - Dynamic and Virtualized Structure of Roads; RD3 - Optimal Infrastructure Design

construct numerous roundabouts for their highway sectors, but often overlook the beneficial characteristics of roundabouts, as these structures have a unique set of design requirements that must be adapted to each road environment [123].

Geometrical factors such as the circle radii, the entry/exit radii, the entry/exit approach width and the direction of the vehicle path have been improved [124], while the link between the speed of the vehicle path configuration through the roundabout and the observed vehicle speeds has been studied.

4 Challenges and Research Directions

In this section, the main challenges and research directions related to the driving model in developing countries are listed. These research directions are mentioned in articles in the reviewed literature or identified based on the own experiences of the authors of this article. All the research directions and work perspectives found have been synthesized in three major research directions that are related to the initial RQ, as illustrated by Table 6.

4.1 RD1: Heterogeneity of traffic entities

Modeling heterogeneous traffic, which includes vehicles such as 2- or 3-wheelers, trucks, and pedestrians, is not completely accurate at the macroscopic and microscopic levels. Empirical evidence indicates that drivers exhibit varied responses when encountering different types of vehicle, particularly in scenarios such as narrow roads or roundabouts, where the geometry of the road affects vehicles differently depending on their maneuverability.

Due to the significant heterogeneity and unique driver behavior on Indian roads, which differs from other developing countries such as China and Indonesia, the principles developed for other countries cannot be easily applied to Indian traffic conditions without establishing suitable adjustment factors. Recognizing this information gap, the CSIR Central Road Research Institute has undertaken the Indonesian HCM project to develop a road capacity manual specifically for Indian conditions, covering the full

1 range of road facilities available in the country [32]. Indonesian HCM considers the
2 heterogeneous traffic conditions commonly found on Indonesian roads. It defines the
3 base conditions for its multipath highways differently, including 3.5 m traffic path or
4 lane widths, shoulders of an effective width of 1.0 m for each road, a divided road, flat
5 terrain, no roadside improvements, very low side grinding, functional class of the road
6 as arterial street and more than 70% of the segment with a view distance greater than
7 300 meters. However, the Indonesian HCM takes into account certain roadside events
8 in the section, such as the presence of pedestrians, stops made by public transport
9 and other vehicles, vehicles entering and leaving roadside premises, and slow moving
10 vehicles, while limiting the weighted frequency of such events to less than 50. Further-
11 more, the Indonesian HCM specifies the sight distance requirements, which are not
12 included in the US-HCM, considering local conditions [32].

13 In the real world, the stochastic environment of vehicle control actions can result
14 in control uncertainty, mainly due to tire slip and brake lock-up. Applying the same
15 acceleration at the same speed could lead to different and often unpredictable out-
16 comes. Consequently, drivers can become uncertain about the specific result of their
17 actions, leading to control uncertainty [72].

18 Among the types of entity that could be found in a traffic system, the autonomous
19 vehicle (AV) has a particular position. In fact, the arrival of AV may constitute another
20 significant turning point in the development of our daily lives, the urban environment,
21 and human civilization as a whole. An extremely disruptive technology, whose use will
22 affect parking problems, air pollution, travel habits, road safety, and other elements
23 of daily life. In developed countries, autonomous vehicles are expected to be widely
24 used for daily transportation in the next ten years. Developing countries would not be
25 able to implement it for at least another fifty years [125]. However, it might soon be
26 used in specific applications [125].

27 The recent study undertaken by Kumar et al. [125] cites the main research direc-
28 tions that researchers could consider. One of them is related to cybersecurity risks. It
29 constitutes one of the main barriers to the adoption of self-driving vehicles, including
30 in developing countries. This study may help explain the interdependence of obstacles
31 for organizations and countries that try to promote the use of autonomous vehicles
32 in developing countries. A policy for autonomous vehicle research must be developed
33 in conjunction with standard testing and homologation procedures. Adopting a leg-
34 islative framework and uniform safety standards is also necessary for organizations
35 and nations. Developing countries must embrace a methodical approach to planning,
36 implementing, and maintaining autonomous vehicles to win consumers' trust and alle-
37 viate concerns about their safety. In a similar approach to the one in this article,
38 Kumar et al. [125] highlight the main obstacles to the general public's acceptance of
39 autonomous vehicles, but it does not provide a numerical estimate of how these obsta-
40 cles will affect the stated goal. Furthermore, the approach has not been statistically
41 tested and is dependent on professional judgment.

44 4.2 RD2: Dynamic and Virtualized Structure of Roads

45 In certain developing countries, such as India, a common feature is the lack of strong
46 lane discipline, resulting in vehicles often straddling between lanes. Empirical evidence
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1 has shown that this results in an increase in road capacity but a decrease in speed
2 profile. Although this phenomenon can be incorporated into macroscopic simulation
3 models through certain adjustments, ongoing research is attempting to model its impli-
4 cations at the microscopic level, such as in trajectory planning and car-following speed
5 adaptation. To advance these studies, an integrated model is necessary, together with
6 further comparisons with field data from different countries.

7 Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) offer considerable potential to
8 change driving behaviors. Their effectiveness is compromised when drivers prone to
9 risky behavior persist in engaging in distracting activities. Although real-time warnings
10 have been shown to improve driving behavior, the sustained impact of warning-based
11 ADAS on curbing driving distractions among light commercial vehicle (LCV) drivers
12 remains uncertain [126]. The findings indicate that warning-based ADAS, which
13 provides real-time alerts, effectively reduces distraction events that lead to driver inat-
14 tention, forward collisions, and lane departures. The research reveals that passive and
15 active monitoring systems, when combined with coaching and rewards, significantly
16 reduce aggressive driving behaviors related to harsh acceleration (by 76%) and harsh
17 braking (by 65%) [126]. These research results offer valuable support to road safety
18 stakeholders in developing countries, helping them develop risk assessments based on
19 warning-based ADAS, launch targeted campaigns to reduce driving distractions, and
20 implement effective driving coaching programs.

21 In countries such as India, numerous road projects have been implemented to
22 facilitate travel and connectivity throughout the country. However, HCM expectations
23 for commercial roads, where lanes are maintained, but road users do not necessarily
24 follow the lane-following pattern, may not always promise the implementation of a
25 good leader-follower model. One such project in India is Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak
26 Yojana (PMGSY), which was started in 2000 to connect rural areas with other major
27 roads such as NH and SH to provide easy access for residents to sell and purchase their
28 goods. The project has also improved the standard of living of people by making them
29 more accessible to NH and SH. PMGSY covers the streets of different areas (ODR)
30 and town streets (VR) that have a single path street for two-way traffic, playing a
31 crucial role in connecting rural areas to market communities, the base camp of Taluka,
32 the improvement center of the block, or other primary roads [40]. Although several
33 studies have examined the performance of different roads, such as NH and SH, in terms
34 of service level (LOS), no such examination has been carried out for single-path roads
35 [40]. A road is considered to have good LOS when vehicles travel at their optimal
36 speed or in free flow conditions (FFC), which refers to the condition in which vehicles
37 travel at their ideal speed without being influenced by other vehicle classifications in
38 the same traffic flow [40]. Studies presume that a vehicle should travel in free flow
39 conditions if its speed is not affected by any other vehicle in the traffic flow [40].
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42 4.3 RD3: Optimal Infrastructure Design

44 Efficient models that estimate the capacity of current and future road infrastructure
45 in developing countries do not address the question of optimal design of such infras-
46 tructure. To address this gap, ongoing research is focused on determining the ideal
47 infrastructure configuration in terms of routes, geometry, and signage, while taking
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1 into account the unique characteristics of developing countries, such as specific driver
2 behaviors, heterogeneous traffic, and an existing infrastructure that contains many
3 roundabouts and unsignalized intersections.

4 Investing in technology and infrastructure for the transportation industry requires
5 considering various factors. Developing countries face challenges due to the lack of
6 categorization of land parcels and mixed land use. This leads to the need for new
7 or modified road sections and the interference of heavy and light vehicles on urban
8 roads. This point of view is shared by Kumar et al. [125] and Outay et al. [17]. They
9 highlight a major research challenge related to the requirement of cyber infrastructure.
10 In fact, it constitutes one of the main barriers to the adoption of self-driving vehicles,
11 especially in developing countries. These changes affect (self) driving behavior and
12 can lead to longer commutes and a dangerous impact on drivers.

13 This research study emphasizes the need to understand the land parcels, comply
14 with the required road standards, and consider the environmental impacts and energy
15 consumption. Researchers should focus on the patterns of following new cars to address
16 the impact of these changes on drivers.

17 Some researchers try to overcome the problem of the existence of a cyber infras-
18 tructure by allowing vehicles, and especially autonomous vehicles, to interact directly
19 without information from the cyber infrastructure. For example, [127] considers that
20 intersections are major bottlenecks for road traffic, as well as the source of many
21 accidents. They propose an inter-vehicle scheduling algorithm for intersections of
22 cooperative vehicles in order to maximize the throughput of the intersection. More
23 specifically, they propose an approach based on deep reinforcement learning and
24 Markov Decision Process to efficiently distribute the right-of-way to each vehicle.
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26 5 Related Works

27 The focus of this research is specific. However, several articles have been published,
28 which provides survey articles related to the topics of this article. This section provides
29 a brief overview of these secondary studies.

30 Cidjeu Djeuthie et al. [128] have conducted a short survey with research questions
31 similar to those presented in this article. However, they have focused their study on
32 sub-Saharan countries, when our study has no geographical limitation. There are some
33 similarities in the terminology used, such as the application of multiagent models for
34 spatiotemporal dynamic growth in developing urban areas; the literature does not
35 address the specific focus of this research [129]. For example, previous research on the
36 modeling of driver route choice does not consider the dynamic and virtual infrastruc-
37 ture [130]. The latter study aims to demonstrate the ability to make environmental
38 decisions with the support of travel information that does not align with the point of
39 interest in this research. In the article of Bouhsissin et al. [131] and Zaidan et al. [132],
40 the aim of the study is to highlight and analyze the different types of driver behav-
41 ior, data sources, datasets, characteristics, and artificial intelligence techniques used
42 to classify driver behavior and its performance. Both of these secondary studies do not
43 focus on developing countries and the associated issues. Elamrani Abou El Assad et al.
44 [133] present an SLR of the concept of driving behavior with a holistic approach to the
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1 different aspects of driving behavior analysis, as well as a scheme to guide the future
2 development and implementation of assessment strategies. In the second part of this
3 article, an overview of the literature on machine learning is highlighted. Saleh et al.
4 [134] provides an SLR on the development of sustainable heritage cities in Malaysia
5 without focusing on mobility and driving models. Among the secondary studies found
6 by the authors, none is dedicated to agent-based modeling of traffic and drivers.

7 Regarding the SLR methodology, many secondary studies have been published
8 using this approach. Tchappi et al. [135] have proposed an SLR study on the usage
9 and application of holonic multiagent systems in the fields of traffic and transporta-
10 tion. Mualla et al. [136] have provided a very detailed survey on the modeling and
11 application of drones in civilian applications. Mkhinini et al. [137] provides a com-
12 prehensive review of the combination of the Unified Modeling Language and ontology
13 paradigm. Calvaresi et al. [138] were interested in the design of chatbots with an
14 individual perspective and using the agent-oriented modeling paradigm.

15 6 Conclusion

16 In this research, the survey of behavior models for drivers in developing countries has
17 been extensively studied, with various ideologies and concepts captured to help under-
18 stand the subject matter. The study identified that driver psychosocial behavior plays
19 an important role in altering or improving the road environment with its associated
20 interactors. Various car follower models that are currently adopted or exist in many
21 developing countries were discussed, evaluated, and reviewed. The report also identi-
22 fied various properties that must be considered to adapt a driver model, especially
23 with unsteady traffic flows, excessive approach demand, and varying directional flows
24 at roundabouts. The traffic operations and congestion design process adopted in cer-
25 tain cities in Asia and Africa were very useful to predict and determine the importance
26 of geometric standards on roads, which can play a vital role for any driver behavior
27 model when deployed and tested.

28 The model analyzes indicated that the behavior of drivers in developing countries
29 is more hazardous, or they do not adhere somewhat to the traffic rules. Prompt sugges-
30 tions based on the overall study would be to recommend the future scope of research
31 on traffic environments in countries such as India, the Philippines, Thailand, and parts
32 of Africa. An unprecedented scenario-based driver behavior model is already available
33 for highly developed countries. Coverage of car following models during adverse cli-
34 matic conditions would help identify potential risks and threats faced by drivers and
35 their behavioral condition, which can become a source of information to build future
36 concepts on Lane following models. On this note, if such an initiative takes place, the
37 level of scope of such models can be assessed and recommended to other developing
38 countries.

39 To the researcher's knowledge and awareness, no literature articles are available
40 that summarize and capture the developing country's driving behavior models in one
41 research study. Thus, this research work can benefit future scholars and researchers in
42 identifying this as a basis for further extension. It is essential to note that this research
43 study did not explicitly point out a particular driving behavior model of interest, but
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it captures the essence of various prevalent car following models and driver behavior models associated with developing countries.

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 - Vishal A. Gracian has completed the SLR process as a Master student. He is also the main contributor to the text of the article.
 - Stéphane Galland has realized the SLR process as an expert. He is also the second major contributor to the text of the article. He is the major contributor for the revised text of the article.
 - Alexandre Lombard has performed the SLR process as an expert. He is also the third major contributor to the text of the article.
 - Thomas Martinet has performed the SLR process as an expert. He is also the fourth major contributor to the text of the article.
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References

- [1] O’Sullivan, A., Sheffrin, S.M.: Economics: Principles in Action vol. 07458. Pearson Prentice Hall, ??? (2003)

- 1 [2] Althor, G., Watson, J.E., Fuller, R.A.: Global mismatch between greenhouse
2 gas emissions and the burden of climate change. *Scientific Reports* **6**(1) (2016)
3 <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep20281>
- 4 [3] Dupont, P., Egan, K.: Solving bangkok's transport woes: The need to ask the
5 right questions. *World Transport Policy and Practice* **3**(1), 25–37 (1997)
6
- 7 [4] World Bank: Sustainable Transport: Priorities for Policy Reform
8
- 9 [5] Gakenheimer, R.: Urban mobility in the developing world. *Transportation*
10 *Research Part A* **33**, 671–689 (1999)
11
- 12 [6] Sperling, D., Salon, D.: Transportation in Developing Countries: An Overview
13 of Greenhouse Gas Reduction Strategies. [https://escholarship.org/uc/item/
14 0cg1r4nq](https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0cg1r4nq)
15
- 16 [7] World Health Organization: Global Status Report on Road Safety
17
- 18 [8] Ennajih, D., Elgameh, M., Echchelh, S.A., Chaouch, A.: Study of the influence
19 of parameters of road safety on the road accidents. *Int J Res Stud Sci Eng*
20 *Technol* **2**(4), 22–27 (2015)
21
- 22 [9] Kanagaraj, V., Asaithambi, G., Kumar, C.N., Srinivasan, K.K., Sivanandan, R.:
23 Evaluation of different vehicle following models under mixed traffic conditions.
24 *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences* **104**, 390–401 (2013)
25
- 26 [10] Djeddi, T., Haidouchi, A.: Determination of the main factors of road accidents
27 in algeria during the period algeria. *Sci J Platform* **12**, 21–35 (2015)
28
- 29 [11] Ahmed, D., Dahbia, D., Tebbal, L.: The reality traffic accidents in algeria. a
30 comparative study between algeria and the arab countries and the developed
31 center for promoting ideas. *Int J Bus Social Sci.* **8**, 158 (2017)
32
- 33 [12] Algerian national center for road safe and prevention: Decrease of traffic
34 accidents in algeria. *Atlas Magazine* (2018)
35
- 36 [13] Boufedda, E.: The main causes of road accidents in algeria. *Revue EL Bahith*
37 *en Sciences Humaines et Sociales*, 113–118 (2019)
38
- 39 [14] Ghaweel, I.A., Mursi, S.A., Jack, J.P., Joel, I.: Factors affecting road traffic
40 accidents in benghazi libya. *Libyan J of Medicine* (2008)
41
- 42 [15] Yahia, I.A., Hussin, A.M.: Causes and effects of road traffic accidents in tripoli
43 libya. In: the 6th Civil Engineering Conference in Asia Region (2009)
44
- 45 [16] Tayfour, A., Awadalla, G.A.: Characteristics and prediction of traffic accident
46 casualties in sudan using statistical modeling and artificial neural networks. *Int*
47 *J Transportation Sci Technol* **1**, 305–317 (2012)
48

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47
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53
54
55
56
57
58
59
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65
- [17] Outay, F., Galland, S., Gaud, N., Abbas-Turki, A.: Simulation of connected driving in hazardous weather conditions: General and extensible multiagent architecture and models. *Int. Journal of Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence (EAAI)* **104**, 104412 (2021) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2021.104412>
 - [18] Prabuchandran, K.J., Hemanth Kumar, A.N., Bhatnagar, S.: Multi-agent reinforcement learning for traffic signal control. In: 17th International IEEE Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC), pp. 2529–2534 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ITSC.2014.6958095>
 - [19] Krajzewicz, D., Erdmann, J., Behrisch, M., Bieker, L.: Recent development and applications of SUMO-simulation of urban mobility. *International Journal on Advances in Systems and Measurements* **5**(3&4) (2012)
 - [20] Horni, A., Nagel, K., Axhausen, K.W.: *The Multi-Agent Transport Simulation MATSim*. Ubiquity Press, London, GBR (2016)
 - [21] Wooldridge, M.: *An Introduction to Multiagent Systems*. John Wiley & Sons, ??? (2009)
 - [22] Weiss, G., al.: *Multiagent systems. Intelligent Robotics and Autonomous Agents* (2013)
 - [23] Munigety, C.R., Mathew, T.V.: Towards behavioral modeling of drivers in mixed traffic conditions. *Transportation in Developing Economies* **2**(1), 1–20 (2016)
 - [24] Budgen, D., Brereton, P.: Performing systematic literature reviews in software engineering. In: the 28th International Conference on Software Engineering, pp. 1051–1052. ACM, ??? (2006)
 - [25] Kitchenham, B.A., Brereton, P., Turner, M., Niazi, M.K., Linkman, S., Pretorius, R., Budgen, D.: Refining the systematic literature review process—two participant-observer case studies. *Empir. Softw. Eng.* **15**(6), 618–653 (2010)
 - [26] Kitchenham, B., Charters, S.: *Guidelines for Performing Systematic Literature Reviews in Software Engineering*
 - [27] Mualla, Y., Najjar, A., Daoud, A., Galland, S., Nicolle, C., Yasar, A.-U.-H., Shakshuki, E.: Agent-based simulation of unmanned aerial vehicles in civilian applications: A systematic literature review and research directions. *Future Generation Computer Systems* **100**, 344–364 (2019) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2019.04.051> . Scimago/WOS Q-Indexes: Q1, Impact factor: 7.187
 - [28] Brereton, P., Kitchenham, B.A., Budgen, D., Turner, M., Khalil, M.: Lessons from applying the systematic literature review process within the software engineering domain. *Journal of Systems and Software* **80**(4), 571–583 (2007)

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- [29] Galster, M., Weyns, D., Tofan, D., Michalik, B., Avgeriou, P.: Variability in software systems - a systematic literature review. *IEEE Trans. Softw. Eng.* **40**(3), 282–306 (2014)
- [30] Calvaresi, D., Cesarini, D., Sernani, P., Marinoni, M., Dragoni, A.F., Sturm, A.: Exploring the ambient assisted living domain: a systematic review. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing* **8**(2), 239–57 (2017)
- [31] Siva, S., Prasad, G., Surisetty, R., Ch, S.: A study on gap-acceptance of unsignalized intersection under mixed traffic conditions. *Int. J. of Research in Engineering and Technology* (2014)
- [32] Arun, A., Senathipathi, V., Madhu, E.: Methodological framework towards roadway capacity estimation for indian multi-lane highways. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* **104**, 477–486 (2013) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.11.141>
- [33] Giuffrè, O., Grana, A., Tumminello, M., Sferlazza, A.: Estimation of passenger car equivalents for single-lane roundabouts using a microsimulation-based procedure. *Expert Systems with Applications* **79** (2017) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2017.03.003>
- [34] Thunig, T., Nagel, K.: Braess’s paradox in an agent-based transport model. *Procedia Computer Science* **83**, 946–951 (2016) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2016.04.190> . The 7th International Conference on Ambient Systems, Networks and Technologies (ANT 2016) / The 6th International Conference on Sustainable Energy Information Technology (SEIT-2016) / Affiliated Workshops
- [35] Bayomy, A., Gomaa, W.: Car following regime taxonomy based on markov switching. In: *Proceedings of the 17th IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems* (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ITSC.2014.6957871>
- [36] Zhuge, C., Bithell, M., Shao, C., Li, X., Gao, J.: An improvement in MATSim computing time for large-scale travel behaviour microsimulation. *Transportation* (2019) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11116-019-10048-0>
- [37] Ochungo, A.E.: Decongestion of nairobi-thika highway-outer ring road “gsu” intersection using microsimulation and geometric modeling. *American Journal of Water Resources* **8**(2), 45–55 (2020) <https://doi.org/10.12691/ajwr-8-2-1>
- [38] Maurya, A., Budhkar, A.: Development of simulation model for heterogeneous traffic with no lane discipline. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* **104**, 360–369 (2013) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.11.129>
- [39] Papathanasopoulou, V., Antoniou, C.: Flexible car-following models for mixed traffic and weak lane-discipline conditions. *European Transport Research*

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51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- [40] Boora, A., Ghosh, I., Chandra, S.: Identification of free flowing vehicles on two lane intercity highways under heterogeneous traffic condition. *Transportation Research Procedia* **21**, 130–140 (2017) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2017.03.083> . International Symposia of Transport Simulation (ISTS) and the International Workshop on Traffic Data Collection and its Standardization (IWTDCS)
- [41] Arkatkar, S.: Traffic operations and capacity analysis in india. *Transportation Letters* **10**, 65–67 (2018) <https://doi.org/10.1080/19427867.2017.1374007>
- [42] Morita, H., Inenaga, S., Takano, T.: Microsimulation for mixed traffic flow at intersection area in bangkok. In: 2019 First International Conference on Smart Technology Urban Development (STUD), pp. 1–6 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1109/STUD49732.2019.9018840>
- [43] Waizman, G., Shoval, S., Benenson, I.: Traffic accident risk assessment with dynamic microsimulation model using range-range rate graphs. *Accident Analysis & Prevention* **119**, 248–262 (2018) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2018.07.027>
- [44] Jima, D.: Review on factors causes road traffic accident in africa. *Journal of Civil Engineering Research & Technology* **2**, 41–49 (2019)
- [45] Pilko, H., Mandžuka, S., Barić, D.: Urban single-lane roundabouts: a new analytical approach using multi-criteria and simultaneous multi-objective optimization of geometry design, efficiency and safety. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies* **80**, 257–271 (2017) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2017.04.018>
- [46] Serag, M.: Gap-acceptance behavior at uncontrolled intersections in developing countries. *Malaysian Journal of Civil Engineering* **27**(1), 80–93 (2015)
- [47] Arafa, A., Saleh, L.H., Senosy, S.A.: Age-related differences in driving behaviors among non-professional drivers in egypt. *PLOS ONE* **15**(9), 1–9 (2020) <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0238516>
- [48] Yao, W., Zeng, Q., Lin, Y., Xu, D., Zhao, H., Guillemard, F., Geronimi, S., Aioun, F.: On-road vehicle trajectory collection and scene-based lane change analysis : Part II. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* **18**, 1–15 (2016) <https://doi.org/10.1109/TITS.2016.2571724>
- [49] Zhao, H., Wang, C., Lin, Y., Guillemard, F., Geronimi, S., Aioun, F.: On-road vehicle trajectory collection and scene-based lane change analysis: Part I. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* **18**, 1–14 (2016) <https://doi.org/10.1109/TITS.2016.2571726>

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- [50] Al-Jameel, H., Kadhim, A.: Rural traffic characteristics using field data and the developed simulation model. In: IOP Conference on Materials Science and Engineering (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/888/1/012058>
- [51] Gupta, N.: Microscopic traffic simulation using vanets traffic simulator VISSIM. *Int. J. of Research in Engineering and Technology* **03**, 56–58 (2014) <https://doi.org/10.15623/ijret.2014.0326012>
- [52] Hunt, M., Harper, D.N., Lie, C.: Mind the gap: Training road users to use speed and distance when making gap-acceptance decisions. *Int. J. Accident, analysis and prevention* **43**, 2015–202358 (2011) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2011.05.020>
- [53] Dutta, M., Ahmed, M.: Gap acceptance behaviour of drivers at uncontrolled T-intersections under mixed traffic conditions. *Journal of Modern Transportation* **26** (2017) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40534-017-0151-9>
- [54] Kwakwa, O., Adams, C., Ackaah, W., Oliver-Commey, Y.: Signalization options to improve capacity and delay at roundabouts through microsimulation approach: A case study on arterial roadways in ghana. *Journal of Traffic and Transportation Engineering* (2019) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtte.2019.06.003>
- [55] Mulla, A., Joshi, A., Chavan, R., Chakraborty, D., Manjunath, D.: A microscopic model for lane-less traffic. *IEEE Transactions on Control of Network Systems* (2018) <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCNS.2018.2834313>
- [56] Messaoudi, O.: An optimal velocity robust car-following model with consideration of control uncertainty. In: 2018 International Conference on Applied Smart Systems (ICASS), pp. 1–8 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICASS.2018.8652077>
- [57] Altamira, A., García Ramírez, Y., Echaveguren, T., Marcet, J.: Acceleration and deceleration patterns on horizontal curves and their tangents on two-lane rural roads. In: Proceedings of the 93rd Annual Meeting of the Transportation Research Board (2014)
- [58] Hoogendoorn, R.G., Arem, B., Hoogendoorn, S.: Incorporating driver distraction in car-following models: Applying the TCI to the IDM. In: Proceedings of the 2013 IEEE Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems, pp. 2274–2279 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ITSC.2013.6728566>
- [59] Li, G., Pan, Y., Yang, Z., Ma, J.: Modeling vehicle merging position selection behaviors based on a finite mixture of linear regression models. *IEEE Access* (2019) <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2950444>
- [60] Yu, C., Wang, J.: Drivers’ car-following correlative behavior with preceding vehicles in multilane driving. In: Proceedings of the 2014 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium, pp. 64–69 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1109/IVS.2014.6856494>

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55
56
57
58
59
60
61
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63
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65
- [61] Vladislavljevic, I., Cooper, J.M., Martin, P.T., Strayer, D.L.: Importance of integrating driving and traffic simulations: case study of impact of cell phone drivers on traffic flow. In: Proceedings of 88th Annual Meeting of the Transportation Research Board, Washington D.C., USA (2009)
 - [62] Farah, H., Polus, A., Bekhor, S., Toledo, T.: Study of passing gap acceptance behaviour using a driving simulator. *Adv. Transp. Stud. Int. J.*, 9–16 (2007). Special Issue
 - [63] Engel, D., Curio, C.: Detectability prediction in dynamic scenes for enhanced environment perception. In: Proceedings of 2012 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ivs.2012.6232267>
 - [64] Mehar, A., Chandra, S., Velmurugan, S.: Highway capacity through vissim calibrated for mixed traffic conditions. *KSCE Journal of Civil Engineering* **18**(2), 639–645 (2014)
 - [65] Fellendorf, M., Vortisch, P.: Microscopic traffic flow simulator VISSIM. *Fundamentals of traffic simulation*, 63–93 (2010)
 - [66] Papathanasopoulou, V., Antoniou, C.: Flexible car-following models on mixed traffic trajectory data. In: Proceedings of the 96th Annual Meeting of the Transportation Research Board (2017)
 - [67] Siddharth, S., G., R.: Calibration of VISSIM for indian heterogeneous traffic conditions. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* **104**, 380–389 (2013)
 - [68] Rasouli, S., Timmermans, H.: Activity-based models of travel demand promises, progress and prospects. *Int. J. Urban Sci.* **18**(1), 31–60 (2014)
 - [69] Ziemke, D., Nagel, K., Bhat, C.: Integrating CEMDAP and MATSim to increase the transferability of transport demand models. *Transp. Res. Rec. J. Transp. Res. Board* **2493**, 117–125 (2015)
 - [70] Castiglione, J., Grady, B., Bowman, J., Bradley, M., Lawe, S.: Building an integrated activity-based and dynamic network assignment model. In: Proceedings of the 3rd Transportation Research Board Conference on Innovations in Travel Modeling (2010)
 - [71] Roughgarden, T.: On the severity of braess’s paradox: Designing networks for selfish users is hard. *Journal of Computer and System Sciences* **72**(5), 922–953 (2006). Special Issue on FOCS 2001
 - [72] Messaoudi, O., Lahlouhi, A.: An agent-based intervehicle cooperative robust car-following model for longitudinal control under uncertainty. *Int. J. Computer Applications in Technology* **58**(2), 150–164 (2018)

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64
65
- [73] Wiedemann, R.: Simulation des strassenverkehrsflusses. Band 8, Schriftenreihe des Instituts für Verkehrswesen der Universität Karlsruhe, Karlsruhe, Germany (1974)
 - [74] Gipps, P.G.: A behavioural car-following model for computer simulation. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological* **15**(2), 105–111 (1981) [https://doi.org/10.1016/0191-2615\(81\)90037-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0191-2615(81)90037-0)
 - [75] Kraus, S.: *Microscopic Modeling of Traffic Flow: Investigation of Collision Free Vehicle Dynamics*
 - [76] Treiterer, J.: *Investigation of Traffic Dynamics by Aerial Photogrammetric Techniques*
 - [77] Wu, F., Stern, R., Churchill, M., Work, D.: Measuring trajectories and fuel consumption in oscillatory traffic: Experimental results. In: *Proc. 96 Th Annu. Meeting Transp. Res. Board*, pp. 1–14 (2017)
 - [78] Asaithambi, G., Kanagaraj, V., Srinivasan, K., Sivanandan, R.: Study of traffic flow characteristics using different vehicle-following models under mixed traffic conditions. *Transp. Lett.* **10**(2), 92–103 (2016) <https://doi.org/10.1080/19427867.2016.1190887>
 - [79] Benzoni-Gavage, S., Colombo, R.M.: An n-populations model for traffic flow. *Eur. J. Appl. Math.* **14**(5), 587–612 (2003)
 - [80] Clark, S.: Traffic prediction using multivariate nonparametric regression. *J. Transp. Eng.* **129**(2), 161–168 (2003)
 - [81] Han, K., Sun, Y., Liu, H., Friesz, T.L., Yao, T.: A bi-level model of dynamic traffic signal control with continuum approximation. *Transp. Res. Part C, Emerg. Technol.* **55**, 409–431 (2015)
 - [82] Chen, L.W., Chang, C.C.: Cooperative traffic control with green wave coordination for multiple intersections based on the internet of vehicles. *IEEE Trans. Syst. Man Cybern.: Syst.* **47**(7), 1321–1335 (2017)
 - [83] White, R.H., Spengler, J.D., Dilwali, K.M., Barry, B.E., Samet, J.M.: Report of workshop on traffic, health, and infrastructure planning. *Arch. Environ. Occup. Health* **60**(2), 70–76 (2005)
 - [84] Bhavathrathan, B., Mallikarjuna, C.: Evolution of macroscopic models for modeling the heterogeneous traffic: An indian perspective. *Transp. Lett.* **4**(1), 29–39 (2012)
 - [85] Waizman, G., Shoval, S., Benenson, I.: Micro-simulation model for assessing the risk of vehicle–pedestrian road accidents. *J. Intell. Transp. Syst. Technol. Plan.*

Oper. **19** (2014)

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12
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47
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49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- [86] Gibson, J.J.: The Ecological Approach to Visual Perception, 1st edition edn. Psychology Press. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315740218>
- [87] Scarsini, M., Schröder, M., Tomala, T.: Dynamic atomic congestion games with seasonal flows. In: HEC Paris Research Papers (2013)
- [88] Braess, D.: Über ein paradoxon aus der verkehrsplanung. Unternehmensforschung **12**, 258–268 (1968)
- [89] Rossi, R., Gastaldi, M., Meneguzzer, C., Gecchele, G.: Gap-acceptance behavior at a priority intersection: field observations versus experiments of a driving simulator. In: Proceedings of the 90th Transportation Research Board Meeting (2011)
- [90] Kim, H., Miranda Anon, A., Misu, T., Li, N., Tawari, A., Fujimura, K.: Look at me: Augmented reality pedestrian warning system using an in-vehicle volumetric head up display. In: Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces, pp. 294–298. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2856767.2856815>
- [91] Grácio, B.J.C., Wentink, M., Valente Pais, A.R.: Driver behavior comparison between static and dynamic simulation for advanced driving maneuvers. Presence Teleop. Virt. Environ. **20**(2), 143–161 (2011) <https://doi.org/10.1162/pres.a.00040>
- [92] Saifuzzaman, M., Zheng, Z.: Incorporating human factors in car-following models: a review of recent developments and research needs. Transportation research part C: emerging technologies **48**, 379–403 (2014)
- [93] Fitzpatrick, K., Elefteriadou, L., Harwood, D.W., Collins, J.M., McFadden, J., Anderson, I.B., Krammes, R.A., Irizarry, N., Parma, K.D., Bauer, K.M., Passetti, K.: Speed Prediction for Two-Lane Rural Highways
- [94] Pérez, A.M., García, A., Torregrosa, F.J., D’Attoma, P.: Modeling operating speed and deceleration on two-lane rural roads with global positioning system data. Transportation Research Record (2171), 11–20 (2010)
- [95] Hu, W., Donnell, E.T.: Models of acceleration and deceleration rates on a complex two lane rural highway: results from a nighttime driving experiment. Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour **13**(6), 397–406 (2010)
- [96] Bennett, C.R.: A Speed Prediction Model for Rural Two-lane Highways
- [97] Connelly, M.L., Conaglen, H.M., Parsonson, B.S., Isler, R.B.: Child pedestrian’s

- crossing gap thresholds. *Accid. Anal. Prev* **30**, 443–453 (1998)
- [98] Hoffman, E.R., Payne, A., Prescott, S.: Children’s estimates of vehicle approach times. *Hum. Factors* **22**, 235–240 (1980)
- [99] McKelvey, R.K.: Can children learn to discriminate safe road-crossing intervals? *J. Safety Res.* **15**, 57–67 (1984)
- [100] Oxley, J., Fildes, B.N., Ihsen, E., Charlton, J.L., Day, R.H.: Crossing roads safely: an experimental study of age differences in gap selection by pedestrians. *Accid. Anal. Prev.* **27**, 962–971 (2005)
- [101] Plumert, J.M., Kearney, J.K., Cremer, J.F.: Children’s perception of gap affordances: bicycling across traffic-filled intersections in an immersive virtual environment. *Child Dev.* **75**, 1243–1253 (2004)
- [102] Simpson, G., Johnston, L., Richardson, M.: An investigation of road crossing in a virtual environment. *Accid. Anal. Prev.* **35**, 787–796 (2003)
- [103] Drew, D.R.: *Traffic Flow Theory and Control*. McGraw-Hill, ??? (1968)
- [104] Arasan, V.T., Arkatkar, S.S.: Microsimulation study of effect of volume and road width on PCU of vehicles under heterogeneous traffic. *Journal of Transportation Engineering* **136**(12), 1110–1119 (2010) [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)TE.1943-5436.0000176](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)TE.1943-5436.0000176)
- [105] Tanner, J.C.: A theoretical analysis of delays at an uncontrolled intersection. *Biometrika* **49**(1/2), 163 (1962)
- [106] Smeed, R.J.: Road capacity of city centers. *Traffic Engineering and Control* **8**(7) (1966)
- [107] Chaudhry, M.S., Ranjitkar, P.: Capacity analysis of signalised intersection using microsimulation. In: *Proceedings of the 32nd Australasian Transport Research Forum (ATRF)*, Auckland, Australia (2009)
- [108] Eleftheriadou, L.: *An Introduction to Traffic Flow Theory*. Springer, ??? (2011)
- [109] Rodegerdts, L.A., Malinge, A., Marnell, P.S., al.: *Accelerating Roundabouts in the United States*
- [110] *Transportation Research Board: Highway Capacity Manual (HCM) 2010*
- [111] Dahl, J., Lee, C.: Empirical estimation of capacity for roundabouts using adjusted gap acceptance parameters for trucks. *Transp. Res. Rec.* (2312), 34–45 (2012)

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51
52
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56
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59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- [112] Al-Madani, H.M.N.: Dynamic vehicular delay comparison between a police-controlled roundabout and a traffic signal. *Transp. Res. Part A: Policy Prac.* **37**(8), 681–688 (2003)
- [113] Easa, S.M., Mehmood, A.: Optimizing geometric design of roundabouts: multi-objective analysis. *Can. J. Civil Eng.* **33**(1), 29–40 (2006)
- [114] Ma, W., al.: Integrated optimization of lane markings and timings for signalized roundabouts. *Transp. Res. Part C: Emer.* **36**, 307–323 (2013)
- [115] Vasconcelos, A., Seco, A., Silva, A.: Comparison of procedures to estimate critical headways at roundabouts. *Promet* **25**(1), 43–53 (2013)
- [116] Mauro, R., Cattani, M.: Functional and economic evaluations for choosing road intersection layout. *Promet* **24**(5), 441–448 (2012)
- [117] Mandavilli, S., McCartt, A.T., Retting, R.A.: Crash patterns and potential engineering countermeasures at maryland roundabouts. *Traffic Inj. Prev.* **10**(1), 44–50 (2009)
- [118] Kim, S., Choi, J.: Safety analysis of roundabout designs based on geometric and speed characteristics. *KSCE J. Civil Eng.* **17**, 1446–1454 (2013)
- [119] Soren, U.: Safety effects of converting intersections to roundabouts. *Trans. Res. Rec.* **2389**, 22–29 (2013)
- [120] Mauro, R.: *Calculation of Roundabouts - Capacity, Waiting Phenomena and Reliability*. Springer, ??? (2010)
- [121] Montella, A., al.: International overview of roundabout design practices and insights for improvement of the italian standard. *Can. J. Civil Eng.* **40**(12), 1215–1226 (2013)
- [122] Yap, Y.H., Gibson, H.M., Waterson, B.J.: An international review of roundabout capacity modelling. *Transp. Rev.* **33**(5), 593–616 (2013)
- [123] Surdonja, S., Deluka-Tibljias, A., Babic, S.: Optimization of roundabout design elements. *Tehnicki vjesnik-Technical Gazzette* **20**(3), 533–539 (2013)
- [124] Pilko, H., Brcic, D., Subic, N.: Study of vehicle speed in the design of roundabouts. *GRADEVINAR* **66**(5), 407–416 (2014)
- [125] Kumar, G., James, A.T., Choudhary, K., Sahai, R., Song, W.K.: Investigation and analysis of implementation challenges for autonomous vehicles in developing countries using hybrid structural modeling. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* **185**, 122080 (2022) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.122080>
- [126] Masello, L., Sheehan, B., Castignani, G., Shannon, D., Murphy, F.: On the

1 impact of advanced driver assistance systems on driving distraction and risky
2 behaviour: An empirical analysis of Irish commercial drivers. *Accident Analysis
3 & Prevention* **183**, 106969 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2023.106969>

- 4 [127] Lombard, A., Noubli, A., Abbas-Turki, A., Gaud, N., Galland, S.: Deep reinforce-
5 ment learning approach for V2X managed intersections of connected vehicles.
6 *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* **24**(7), 7178–7189
7 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1109/TITS.2023.3253867>
- 8 [128] Cidjeu Djeuthie, D., Wakponou Addie Bernice, N., Tchappi, I., Mualla, Y.,
9 Najjar, A., Galland, S.: Intelligent transportation systems in developing coun-
10 tries: Challenges and prospects. In: 20th International Conference on Mobile
11 Systems and Pervasive Computing (MobiSPC-23). Elsevier, Halifax, Nova Sco-
12 tia, Canada (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2023.09.030> . [https://www.
13 sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877050923010773](https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877050923010773)
- 14 [129] Zhang, H., Jin, X., Wang, L., al.: Multi-agent based modeling of spatiotemporal
15 dynamical urban growth in developing countries: simulating future scenarios
16 of lianyungang city, china. *Stoch. Environ. Res. Risk Assess.* **29**, 63–78 (2015)
17 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00477-014-0942-z>
- 18 [130] Dia, H.: An agent-based approach to modelling driver route choice behaviour
19 under the influence of real-time information. *Transportation Research Part
20 C: Emerging Technologies* **10**(5/6), 331–349 (2002) [https://doi.org/10.1016/
21 S0968-090X\(02\)00025-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0968-090X(02)00025-6)
- 22 [131] Bouhsissin, S., Sael, N., Benabbou, F.: Driver behavior classification: A sys-
23 tematic literature review. *IEEE Access* **PP** (2023) [https://doi.org/10.1109/
24 ACCESS.2023.3243865](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3243865)
- 25 [132] Zaidan, R.A., Alamoodi, A.H., Zaidan, B.B., Zaidan, A.A., Albahri, O.S., Talal,
26 M., Garfan, S., Sulaiman, S., Mohammed, A., Kareem, Z.H., Malik, R.Q.,
27 Ameen, H.A.: Comprehensive driver behaviour review: Taxonomy, issues and
28 challenges, motivations and research direction towards achieving a smart trans-
29 portation environment. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence* **111**,
30 104745 (2022) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2022.104745>
- 31 [133] Elamrani Abou El Assad, Z., Mousannif, H., Al Moatassime, H., Karkouch, A.:
32 The application of machine learning techniques for driving behavior analysis:
33 A conceptual framework and a systematic literature review. *Engineering Appli-
34 cations of Artificial Intelligence* **87**, 103312 (2020) [https://doi.org/10.1016/j.
35 engappai.2019.103312](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2019.103312)
- 36 [134] Saleh, Y., Mahat, H., Hashim, M., Nayan, N., Suhaily, S., Khairul Anuar Ghaz-
37 ali, M., Hayati, R., Kurnia Sri Utami, R.: A systematic literature review (slr) on
38 the development of sustainable heritage cities in Malaysia. *Journal of Regional
39 and City Planning* **32**(3) (2021) <https://doi.org/10.5614/jpww.2021.32.3.6>

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47
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49
50
51
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56
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58
59
60
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62
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65
- [135] Tchappi, I., Galland, S., Kamla, V.C., Kamgang, J.-C., Mualla, Y., Najjar, A., Hilaire, V.: A critical review of holonic technology in traffic and transportation fields. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence* **1-54**(90), 1–54 (2020) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2020.103503>
 - [136] Mualla, Y., Najjar, A., Daoud, A., Galland, S., Nicolle, C., Yasar, A.-U.-H., Shakshuki, E.: Agent-based simulation of unmanned aerial vehicles in civilian applications: A systematic literature review and research directions. *Future Generation Computer Systems* **100**, 344–364 (2019) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2019.04.051>
 - [137] Mkhinini, M.M., Narsis Labbani, O., Nicolle, C.: Combining UML and ontology: An exploratory survey. *Computer Science Review* **35**(100223) (2020) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosrev.2019.100223>
 - [138] Calvaresi, D., Eggenschwiler, S., Mualla, Y., Schumacher, M.I., Calbimonte, J.-P.: Exploring agent-based chatbots: a systematic literature review. *Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing* (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12652-023-04626-5>

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RESPONSES TO REVIEWERS' COMMENTS AND REVISED MANUSCRIPT

Title of the Manuscript:

Behavioral Models of Drivers in Developing Countries with an Agent-based Perspective: A Literature Review

Ref: ATIS-S-23-00018

Authors:

Vishal A. Gracian, Stéphane Galland, Alexandre Lombard, Thomas Martinet, Nicolas Gaud, Hui Zhao, Ansar-UI-Haque Yasar

Dear Editors-in-Chief,

We would like to thank the reviewers for their valuable comments on our paper. We sincerely appreciate them in order to increase the quality of our paper. The paper has been updated according to the comments provided on the original version. The comments lead us to update several points in the paper to answer all the reviewers' comments.

In the rest of this document, we answer the remarks of the editor and the reviewers about our paper, and present a list of the major changes that have been introduced in the new version of the paper. *A copy of the revised manuscript with the changes highlighted in different colors is provided in addition to the revised manuscript with a regular black color font.*

Best regards,

Prof. dr. Stéphane Galland
(on behalf of the authors)

Reviewers' comments:

General reply to all reviewers:

The reviewers have suggested several presentational issues that need addressing. To address these points, we have added new content. This content is highlighted with different colors (one for each reviewer) and prefixed with the identifier(s) of the associated reviewers' comments. In the case that a change concerns multiple reviewers' comments, the text is written in **MAGENTA** font color.

Reviewer #1:

Dear Reviewer #1, we would like to thank you for your evaluation. The changes applied to the paper's text are highlighted in **BLUE** font color and prefixed with the identifier of your comment in the revised paper. Below, you could find your comments (text in the boxes) with its identifier (above each box) and our answers (text below the box).

R1-1

This paper presents a literature review regarding behavioral models of drivers in developing countries with an agent-based perspective. Some comments are listed as follows:

1. In Subsection 2.1, four key research questions are proposed. What is the basis for raising these questions, why is it key to say that these problems?

Basically, the presented problems arise from last decade experiences of the authors who have encountered difficulties to apply main stream mobility models on projects that are deployed in developing countries. Most of the time these main stream mobility models were designed with assumptions that are relevant in developed countries but not in developing countries. For example, the notion of emergent road were introduced in several models for representing the fact that roads are dynamically appearing in African countries depending on the density of vehicles, bikes and pedestrians who are present in the area. In other words, the traffic flow is not restricted to the road infrastructure but may be present on the sideways or simply on the side of the roads. The various experience of the authors leads them to ask the question: what are the specific mobility behaviors in developing countries? And, then what are the existing models of them? Additionally, we are working on fine grained simulation of mobility, using agent-oriented modeling paradigm in order to understand the atomic events, individual behaviors and their interactions. Therefore, the question of agent-centric models in this context is introduced in the SLR. We have updated Section 2.1 to explain the general genesis of the research questions.

R1-2

In Table 1, 82 papers are listed, which are used to statistical analysis, whether the sample is sufficient?

According to SLR [27], the methodology does not try to obtain a huge number of papers for statistical reasons. The purpose is to take a picture of the current state of the literature regarding several research questions using a reproducible methodology. However, the selection of the search keywords is a key point. The queries have provided more than 1000 entries all the search engines. However, according to SLR, we have applied a stop criteria for limiting the number of papers in the study. This stop criteria is defined by: only the first 25 pages of the Google Scholar and Academia databases were considered, all the pages on IEEE database were considered. We have updated Section 2.2.1 to highlight this specific point of the SLR methodology.

R1-3

Section 5 has few research content, the related works of the authors' team can be introduced in detail, highlighting the contributions.

We have assumed that the related works on this paper are similar studies, i.e., secondary studies. We consider that the description of the models in details is not the purpose of this article, that is to provide an overview of the state-of-the-art and several major research directions that may be selected for doing doctoral studies. However, we have updated Section 5 for provided recent references to secondary studies.

R1-4

The discussion of challenges and research directions can be detailed, e.g., the effect of autonomous vehicles on traffic.

Thank you for your valuable comment. We have updated Section 4.1 and 4.3 and provided a more detailed discussion, especially related to autonomous vehicles.

Reviewer #2:

Dear Reviewer #2, we would like to thank you for your evaluation. The changes applied to the paper's text are highlighted in **GREEN** font color and prefixed with the identifier of your comment in the revised paper. Below, you could find your comments (text in the boxes) with its identifier (above each box) and our answers (text below the box).

R2-1

The entire content is quite detailed, with relatively rare research on transportation models in developing countries. The way the questions are posed to summarize the content of the review article is rather creative. However, there is a noticeable gap when compared to conventional high-level academic papers, especially in terms of language expression. The contributions throughout the paper lack precision and conciseness, making the article appear less impactful.

1. The organization of the introduction needs improvement; many statements lack relevance to the main topic of this article. It is advisable to succinctly state the purpose and contributions of the review. Please eliminate irrelevant content, such as: "These countries generally share common health challenges, such as lack of access to safe drinking water, sanitation and hygiene, as well as energy poverty, high levels of pollution, and high incidence of tropical and infectious diseases [2]."

Thank you for your valuable comment. We have reviewed the text of the introduction and conclusion section in order to focus on the specific topics and research questions of this article.

R2-2

The "contribution" section is too broad and fails to highlight meaningful research questions, resulting in a lack of prominence in this article's research topic.

The contribution of this article is divided in two parts:

- conducting a SLR on the modeling of driving behaviors in developing countries with an agent perspective. According to SLR methodology [27], it must be based on research questions that participate to the global research question. The SLR contribution is there to output a state of the progress from existing articles as clear as possible, without introducing a new contribution. Indeed, SLR is considered as a secondary study, and not a primary study. Your contribution on this first point is detailed in Section 3. Each subsection of Section 3 is dedicated to a specific research question.
- highlighting several research directions that corresponds to a synthesis of the research directions and perspectives that were found in the reviewed papers. This contribution is detailed in Section 4.

We have understood that the contributions are not enough well introduced. Consequently, we have updated the introduction section. We have also updated Section 3. Additionally, we have updated Section 4 to give more details on research directions.

R2-3

Sections 2.2 and 2.3 contain excessive content with low significance. It is recommended to reduce these sections. Placing them at the beginning may distract readers from the essential content of the entire article.

Following the principles of open science, these two sections are needed for enabling any researcher outside the list of the authors to reproduce your research study. It is recommended by SLR [27] to include all these details. We would prefer to keep them inside the article. However, we have reduced the text in Section 2.

R2-4

The extensive blocks of text in the entire article make it difficult for readers to extract crucial information. It is advisable to use charts and graphs to summarize important information after each main section or research question to enhance readability.

Thank you for noticed this problem. We have introduced more synthesized information in Section 3.

R2-5

In the fourth section, "4 Challenges and Research Directions," is there a logical connection between 4.1-4.3 and the research questions (RQ1-RQ4) proposed earlier? If there is, please express it with a framework diagram. If not, it is recommended to address R&D from the perspective of formulating questions.

As you have noticed, there is a possible connection between the research questions and the research directions. However, according to the selected SLR methodology, it is not necessary to have all the research directions connected to the research questions. Indeed, some directions may emerge from the literature papers, and that may be not considered as the initial starting point of the study. Nevertheless, a figure was introduced in Section 4 for making explicit the relationships between the RQs and RDs.

R2-6

The four questions are relatively simple, and the review conducted around these four questions is also superficial, without in-depth analysis of the core and characteristics of the reviewed articles.

Indeed, initially this study was started for understanding the global state of the art related to driving behaviors in developing countries, with the point of view of a incoming research on the field. Research questions were written in order to be large enough to give a broad view of the field. We understand that other SLR on more specific and detail points maybe needed in the

coming months. Nevertheless, to increase readability of Section, we have introduced more tables. This change gives us the opportunity to rephrase the analysis from the reviewed articles.

Reviewer #3:

Dear Reviewer #3, we would like to thank you for your evaluation. The changes applied to the paper's text are highlighted in **RED** font color and prefixed with the identifier of your comment in the revised paper. Below, you could find your comments (text in the boxes) with its identifier (above each box) and our answers (text below the box).

R3-1

I will recommend acceptance of this article but suggest authors to undertake major revision to restructure the article following my suggestion.

The goal is to study impact of driver behavior in developing countries with an Agent-based Perspective.

Originality: [What is the problem? How could we define the problem?]

1. Problem Identification: (To data mine research efforts published between 2010 to 2020 that are related to driver behavior in developing counties with an Agent-based Perspective.)

Thank you for your comment. We have updated the introduction section to enforce the goal of this study and the expected outcomes: a state of the existing works, and a list of research directions.

R3-2

Problem Definition: (tasks are defined in 4 steps; identify the sources for information; means to extract information; analyze the information; and finally draw conclusion on the finding and make recommendation.)

Ability to test ideas: (Perception: How to prove it?)

According to SLR methodology [27], we have described in Section 2 the key elements for the methodology that should make able any research outside the list of the authors to conduct a similar study; and then validate the findings. It is also possible to conduct a another study based on some different elements in the methodology and compare the new findings with those we have written in this article.

R3-3

Constructing a Strategy: (The four tasks are to be completed in order; data sources / data mining the information / analyze the data / draw conclusion and

make recommendation)

As you have noticed, and according to SLR, we have conducted a study based on the four steps:

1. data sources: we have specified in Section 2 the data sources, i.e., the databases from which the articles were collected.
2. Data mining of the information : we have conducted a filtering of the articles based on two steps. The first step is the exclusion of articles based on the reading of the titles, abstract and keywords of each article. The second step is the exclusion of the articles based on the text content. All the relevant articles were included in the analysis. This filtering and analysis were done by two experts for each paper, plus a referee who was in charge of solving any conflict in the reviews provided by the two experts.
3. Analysis of data: Section 3 provides a synthesis of the analysis according to four research questions that are put on table before the study is started.
4. Draw conclusion: your conclusions are mostly synthesis in the highlighting of the research directions in Section 4. Nevertheless, Section 3 also contains some conclusions related to each research question. According to SLR methodology, there is no recommendation strictly speaking. Research directions in Section 4 are the synthesis of perspectives gathered from the reviewed papers.

R3-4

Organizing Information about the Problem: (Data Sources: relevant articles published between 2010 to 2020 with "driver behavior in developing countries" and "ABS" in their titles or abstracts. Extraction Procedure: develop a list of keywords for pattern matching. Data Analysis: compile and consolidate findings into tables. Draw Conclusion: identify the root cause of bad driver behaviors and make recommendation.

See your answer to R3-3 that seems to be relevant to this comment to.

R3-5

Allocation of Resources: (The databases selected for this study were IEEE Xplore, Academia, and Google Scholar.)

We have updated Section 2.2.1, related to the database selection, for giving a more clear explanation relation to the database selection and how they are used.

R3-6

Monitoring Problem Solving: (Findings are presented in tables, but [Table for

RQ2, RQ3 and RQ4 are missing]. There are also errors in Table 3, there are supposed to have 31 articles, not 30, calculation of % also not correct!)

Thank you for noticed this problem. We have fixed it. We have also introduced more tables in Section 3.

R3-7

Evaluating Problem Solving: (Shown in Table 3; 56% pointed to the root cause, or reason of bad driver behaviors are either directly or indirectly link to the landscape and terrains of badly maintain road conditions, and if we taking away the decision-making power from the drivers by the introduction of intervention such as Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS), the percentage increase to 63%, based on the figures in Table 3.] The three recommendations; Heterogeneity of traffic entities; Dynamic and Visualized Structure of Roads; and Optimal Infrastructure Design will be groundless, if there is no well maintain road system to build on.)

We agree you comment. We have updated Section 4 in order to include some research direction to ADAS as a technological tool for helping to solve issues that are specific to mobility behavior in developing countries.

Behavioral Models of Drivers in Developing Countries with an Agent-based Perspective: A Literature Review

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Abstract

The traffic in developing countries presents its own specificity, notably due to the heterogeneous traffic and a weak-lane discipline. This leads to differences in driver behavior between these countries and developed countries. **Knowing that the analysis of the drivers from developed countries leads the design of the majority of driver models, it is not surprising that the simulations performed using these models do not match the field data of the developing countries.** This article presents a systematic review of the literature on modeling driving behaviors in the context of developing countries. **The study focuses on the microsimulation approaches, and specifically on the multiagent paradigm, that are considered suitable for reproducing driving behaviors with accuracy.** The major contributions from the recent literature are analyzed. Three major scientific challenges and related minor research directions are described.

Keywords: Driver Behavior, Developing Country, Microsimulation, Multiagent Systems, Systematic Literature Review Method

1 Introduction

[R2-1]Urbanization is on the rise in developing countries, which are often characterized by their low Human Development Index and trends in nonindustrialized infrastructure [1, 2]. Despite efforts to stimulate economic development, many cities in developing countries face traffic gridlock and struggle to build enough road infrastructure to meet demand [3–5]. Mobility and accessibility are declining in these cities, even as they become more complex [6]. [R3-1]Even if the transportation sector is critical for economic development, informal rules and regulations that can be used in developing countries often make it difficult for road users. Therefore, they face specific challenges [1, 7] in the implementation of mobility and traffic systems. Most urban communities in developing countries have developed without mechanized vehicles and narrow streets without sidewalks. This land use design works well for societies that rely on nonmechanized transportation. However, the growing number of cars is putting pressure on infrastructure, particularly in areas where different types of vehicle share the same roadway. Many cities face challenges related to road safety, such as Delhi, where pedestrians, carts, and vehicles share the same space. Some cities have coped better, such as Shanghai, which has built separate paths for bicycles, slow bikes, and pedestrians. However, there are significant differences in the way vehicles are used and designed in different countries [6]. For example, minivans in South Africa are used for public transportation, although they were not designed for that purpose, and are often overloaded. Traffic patterns in developing countries also generally involve poor lane discipline and heterogeneous traffic, leading to complex interactions between different types of vehicle. In this global context, there has been growing interest in studying driving behavior in developing countries. In fact, road traffic accidents are the leading cause of death and disability among young people aged 15 to 29 years and among the top three causes of mortality among those aged 15 to 44 years [8]. Human factors, such as driver behavior, contribute to road traffic accidents in many African countries, including Morocco, Algeria, Libya, and Sudan [9–16].

In this situation, simulation is a tool that enables one to reproduce and test driver’s behavior and to notice their belongings, without applying them in a genuine rush-hour gridlock environment. Agent-based simulation (ABS) is considered an appropriate paradigm for modeling and simulated traffic systems at the microscopic level [17–20]. [R2-1][R3-1]An agent is characterized as an autonomous entity located in some environment and equipped with the ability to coordinate with other agents to achieve its objectives [21, 22]. ABS reproduces the global behavior of systems from the definition of local behaviors and their interactions in the environment. ABS involves autonomous agents that interact with each other and the environment to achieve their objectives [21, 22]. It can replicate the behavior of the global system by defining local behaviors and their interactions in the environment.

[R2-1]However, most of the existing models (ABS or not) of longitudinal and lateral driver behavior are generally designed for developed countries. They do not adequately capture integrated driving behavior in developing countries [23]. To determine the maturity of the research for modeling the driving behavior in developing countries, a survey should be carried out. Consequently, the objective of this study is two-fold:

- 1) *Conduct a systematic review of the literature* (SLR) addressing various driving behavior models in developing countries. This SLR means to recognize the main exploration questions, investigate the writing, and outline key difficulties and investigation headings.
- 2) Outline and discuss *research directions* with suitable suggestions of driving behaviors that are feasible for a developing country.

This article is structured as follows. Section 2 states and defines the SLR methodology adapted from [24, 25]. Section 3 details the analysis and results of the SLR. Based on these results, Section 4 identifies the main research directions. Section 5 discusses related work. Section 6 concludes this article.

2 Review Methodology

SLR is a popular and efficient strategy for exploring science fields. According to Kitchenham and Charters [26], SLR is a type of secondary investigation that systematically identifies, analyzes and interprets all available evidence related to a specific research question in an unbiased and partially replaceable manner. This study focuses on investigating different models of driving behavior through literature articles to provide recommendations for modeling driving behavior in ABS. The objective of SLR is to summarize current evidence on widely used technology, identify research gaps, and provide a foundation for new research initiatives [24]. To achieve these objectives, the precise literature uses suitable methods to combine SLRs in transportation and computer science [24, 25], ensuring rigor, fairness and reproducibility. Fig. 1 shows the review process.

Fig. 1 Systematic literature review process, from Mualla et al. [27], adapted from Brereton et al. [28], Galster et al. [29]

2.1 Key Research Questions

The research study follows the goal question measure (GQM) proposed by [25] to identify key questions related to driving behavior in developing countries. [R1-1][R2-2]The main challenge is to increase mobility for a large part of the population at reasonable cost without creating environmental problems. Researchers have applied mobility models that were initially designed in the context of developed countries. However, the modeling assumptions used in these models are not relevant to developing countries. For example, the notion of an emerging road was not always supported by these models. It corresponds to roads that appear dynamically depending on the density of vehicles, bikes, and pedestrians present in the area. In other words, traffic flow is not restricted to road infrastructure, but may be present on the sides of the roads themselves. Therefore, driving behavior in these countries tends to be erratic, leading to increased risks that are not fully modeled by existing models. This observation is shared by multiple researchers in the literature. Having described the notions above, our study of interest is divided into several Research Questions (RQs) exploring the main key problems in evaluating various driving behavior models in developing countries. [R1-1][R2-2]Research questions have been selected to provide directions and suggestions related to modeling driving and mobility behaviors in developing countries. A particular focus is on the microscopic behaviors that can be modeled using the agent-oriented paradigm [21, 22]. The formulation of these questions is based on the experience of the reviewers.

RQ1: What are the research topics and application domains of the articles related to the topics of this study? This research question provides an overview of the different research fields considered in the reviewed articles, as well as the associated application domains.

RQ2: What are the existing driver models that represent the behaviors of the drivers in developing countries? This research question occupies the priority, as it leads the rest of the categories of questions for the research study. [R1-1][R2-2]By exploring the kind of driving models popular in developed countries, the literature can be analyzed to understand pre-existing driver behavior models for developing countries. This question can provide ample data that can be analyzed to support an organized pattern in the research study. The preference for the mode of travel of choice among road users in developing countries can also be touched upon if a suitable level of analysis reveals concrete evidence favoring the research question.

RQ3: What are the suitable models for agent-oriented simulation of driving behavior in developing countries, and how can it be implemented into an agent-oriented simulator? This research question aims to investigate the suitability of existing models for ABS and identify a suitable model that can follow a streamlined pattern capable of adaptation in any developing country. The question also aims to address the challenges and limitations in implementing the driving behavior model into an agent-oriented simulator, focusing on the requirements and restrictions. [R1-1][R2-2]The research

will explore the nature of road users and traffic conditions to derive a decisive model of driving behavior and suggest techniques to adapt an ABS for advanced research studies.

RQ4: What kind of driving environment is considered having identified the driver behaviours? This RQ is related to various environmental means that are crucial in affecting the level of service (LOS) or the operation of road service on an urban roadway or dense highways. [R1-1][R2-2]Analysis can reveal the reason for the sustainability of homogeneous or heterogeneous traffic conditions in such a place, keeping in mind the preconceived notion that leads to a network smothering the grid when the traffic stream increases its bandwidth. It should help researchers determine and choose the significant properties exhibited in driver behavior.

2.2 Defining Review Protocol

This section describes the steps of the methodology that are represented in Fig. 1.

2.2.1 Database Selection

The databases selected for this study were IEEE Xplore, Academia, and Google Scholar. Although the first two databases were chosen to obtain specific data related to the researcher's topic, Google Scholar was selected for its vast collection of records, including conference articles, Ph.D. and Master's theses, and extensive research articles. Although not peer reviewed, these articles were considered important given the recent increase in interest in the topic. [R3-5]Databases were queried using a set of keywords, including those related to models of driving behavior and recreation strategies in developing countries, as well as broader trends related to transportation in developing countries. [R1-2]According to SLR methodology, a stop criterion is used to limit the total number of articles that are included in the study from the different databases. For this particular study, we have decided to extract papers from the first 25 pages provided by Google Scholar and Academia, and all the pages provided by IEEE database. This stop criterion is designed to limit the investigation time in the scope of two months, which was the time window allowed in the context of the funding projects in this study.

2.2.2 Keyword Selection

Since the research area is highly focused on developing countries, the first set of keywords used by the authors of this research study decided to formulate it more refined, which helped in fetching scientific articles involved in driving behavior models for developing countries more directly. This led to the first set of keywords: in Equation (1).

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{driving behavior model, driving models developing countries,} \\ \text{car following models India, car following models Africa,} \\ \text{existing lane changing models, lane changing models India,} \\ \text{lane changes in developing country,} \\ \text{lane manoeuvring Africa, gap acceptance models India,} \\ \text{single lane road} \end{array} \right\} \quad (1)$$

After further review and peer discussion, the authors of this study decided to have a more comprehensive keyword set structure that could add more scientific articles. Thus, the second set of keywords was formulated as in Equation (2).

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{agent based model, car following model,} \\ \text{driving behavior, transport simulation model,} \\ \text{gap acceptance model, lane change model,} \\ \text{lane model, lane-less, longitudinal behaviors,} \\ \text{multi agent model, multi lane model,} \\ \text{single lane model, traffic operations,} \\ \text{transport models, transport infrastructure,} \\ \text{transport lane models, transport microsimulation models} \end{array} \right\} \quad (2)$$

2.2.3 Exclusion Criteria Definition

Articles that appear in the indexed lists provided by search engines are not all valuable for responding to the RQ. For this reason, almost all literature review methodologies apply a set of exclusion criteria to retain only relevant articles [29, 30]. The authors of this study have defined the following exclusion criteria:

- ExC1: Not a recent research work.** Articles published before 2010, i.e., with a publication year < 2010, are excluded. It is assumed that the nonrecent research is not up-to-date due to the high evolution rate of the driving behavior models and simulation techniques.
- ExC2: Invalid type of articles, the document is a poster or a demo.** It is assumed that a poster or a demo cannot provide enough details of contributions, as there is not enough contributed content for evaluation. Ph.D. theses, Master theses, and technical reports are included.
- ExC3: Invalid type of article, the article is a survey.** It is assumed that the survey articles (i.e. secondary studies) do not provide contributions directly on the driving behavior models and simulation techniques.
- ExC4: Impossible to access the text of the article.** It is impossible to evaluate an article when its text cannot be accessed (PDF download, online text, etc.).
- ExC5: Exclude articles not specific to developing countries.** Ignore topics that are irrelevant or do not contribute to the support of developing countries.
- ExC6: Extended Article.** The article is extended by another article by the same authors. The contributions in the extended article are enclosing those of the original article, so that the latter is excluded.

ExC7: Exclude articles unrelated to driving behavior. Literature articles that do not support these topics are ignored.

ExC8: Exclude articles with macro- or mesoscopic driving behavior. The proposed models cannot capture the individual properties of the driving behavior.

ExC9: Cannot be applied in developing countries. Exclude articles that address a very specific infrastructure model that seems not suitable for transferring the techniques to developing countries or too advanced, i.e., beyond the scope of current trends in these countries. For example, understanding lane change systems for regular vehicles would be useful for analysis rather than analyzing the implications of lane changes that autonomous vehicles face in a prescribed road environment, which would not be appropriate to transfer or suggest a mechanism of such conditions to a developing country. In simple words, analyzing the behavior of autonomous vehicles in the lane and its microsimulations along with the use of mathematical data would not serve the purpose of this research study, as developing countries have not yet reached that phase.

These rules of exclusion criteria are applied to reports in two stages. In the primary coarse-grained step, the articles were possibly disposed of if their titles and abstracts met at any rate one of the avoidance standards. In the subsequent fine-grained step, the excess articles are screened, however, this time perusing the entire body of the article.

2.2.4 Biases

To mitigate the subjectivity of the review process, certain measures were taken to overcome biases and resolve conflicts. In particular, each selection step was conducted by a principal reviewer, with an associated reviewer who may complete the analysis of the first reviewer. A third reviewer intervened as a referee to resolve a conflict in the exclusion/inclusion and in the research question answering steps.

2.3 Performing the Review

Queries the different search engines with the predefined stop criterion corresponds to 82 articles. Note that since the first selection step screens articles based on their titles and abstracts, some exclusion criteria might be more helpful than others. For this reason, the exclusion criteria ExC1 – ExC4 were applied directly during the extraction of scientific articles, leading to the total number of 77 articles. More specifically, the content of the article is screened and the article is excluded if it satisfies at least one of the exclusion criteria. Table 1 shows the results of the selection steps.

As it is illustrated by Fig. 2, the exclusion criteria indicate that the reviewers are focused on recent primary research studies on microlevel driving behavior models that are applicable to developing countries and provide high-quality and informative contributions. ExC5 and ExC9 exclude the highest number of articles (32, 37%), suggesting that the reviewers focus on driving behavior models and, more specifically, on those that are considered feasible for implementation in developing countries. ExC1, ExC7

Table 1 Number of articles at the different steps of the methodology

Methodology Step	Number of Articles	Percentage
Initial queries in the search engines	82 ¹	100%
Excluded articles	52	63%
Included articles	30	36%

¹10 with the first keyword set, 72 with the second keyword set.

Fig. 2 The number of excluded articles per exclusion criterion

and ExC8 excluded 15 articles (18%), indicating that the authors focus on recent research related to microlevel driving behavior models. ExC2 excluded 2 articles (2%), indicating that only high-quality and informative publications are being considered. ExC3, ExC4 and ExC6 did not exclude any article, suggesting that all articles found were original accessible primary research studies.

Based on Fig. 3, research on driving behavior models in developing countries seems to have started around 2011 with only one article published that year. The number of publications increased over time, reaching a peak in 2014 with five articles. The trend remained relatively stable until 2019, with a slight increase in the number of publications. However, there was a decrease in the number of publications in 2020. The trend line of annual publications has a slope of 0.376 ± 0.18 . This suggests that the topic of driving behavior models in developing countries is gaining more attention and interest from researchers over time.

According to Fig. 4, it appears that most of the articles (8) were published in India, followed by China (6 articles). The rest of the articles seem to be distributed across several countries with only one article each, suggesting that research on driving behavior models in developing countries is still limited and dispersed across different parts of the world. However, it should be noted that, at this stage of the methodology, there is no information on the quality or impact of the article, so it is difficult to draw any definitive conclusions about the research landscape in this field based only on this information.

Fig. 3 Number of articles per year after the selection steps

Fig. 4 Geographic distribution of articles after the selection steps

Fig. 4 shows that the majority of articles (17) focus on driving behavior models in Asia. This is not surprising as Asia is home to many developing countries and is one of the most populous continents in the world. Africa is also well represented in the table with six articles, which is expected given the large number of developing countries in Africa. Europe has five articles, which could suggest that research on driving behavior models is more focused on developed countries in Europe. South America and Oceania have only one article each, which may indicate that there is less research being conducted in these regions on driving behavior models.

In terms of developing countries specifically, both Asia and Africa have a significant number of articles, with a combined total of 23 articles out of 30. This suggests that there is a focus on developing countries in the research on driving behavior models.

[R3-6]

Table 2 The reviewed articles per research topic

Research Topic	Articles	Percentage
T1 - Traffic Network Modeling	[31–36]	20%
T2 - Heterogeneous Traffic Flow Modeling	[37–42]	20%
T3 - Road Safety	[43–45]	10%
T4 - Individual Driving Behavior Modeling	[46–57]	40%
T5 - Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS)	[58–60]	10%

However, it is important to note that the table does not provide information on the specific countries that are being studied within each continent, and therefore it is not possible to draw conclusions about the distribution of research across different developing countries.

3 Results of the Review and Analysis

[R2-2]In this section, we present a comprehensive examination of the results obtained from the SLR. The articles retained after the selection process are examined, and each RQ defined in Section 2.1 is discussed in detail. It is important to note that the results are relevant to the driving behavior models observed in developing countries and their incorporation into an ABS, according to RQ and the exclusion criteria defined in the SLR methodology.

3.1 What are the research topics and application domains of the articles related to the topics of this study? (RQ1)

This section discusses the results and answers RQ1 (cf. Section 2.1). It deals with research topics (Section 3.1.1) along with application domains (Section 3.1.2).

3.1.1 Research Topics

[R2-2]Research topics are the subjects or issues that a researcher is interested in when directing the exploration of driving behavior models. They provide general guidance to investigators in characterizing and refining their thoughts. Table 2 and Fig. 5 represent the research topics of the articles reviewed in the study. These topics cover different aspects related to driving behavior models and simulation techniques, such as traffic flow and network analysis, driver behavior and psychosocial aspects, vehicle speed, and advanced driver assistance systems. Details on each topic are provided below.

- T1: Traffic Network Modeling.** [R2-2]Travel choice comes into play when defining a traffic network [34–36] that forecast the behavior of the system using timestep approach and ABS. Among the articles that are found in this research topic, several focus on the Highway Capacity Manual (HCM) [31–33], which is a conflicting technique that uses the Tanner formula to determine the capacities of the roads.
- T2: Heterogeneous Traffic Flow.** Mixed traffic flow is always prevalent with sensitized urban road flow, which is primarily prone to congestion [37–42]. [R2-2]Usually, the capacity for traffic and the level of service in traffic operations all

Fig. 5 [R3-6] Number of articles per research topics

hinder the free flow condition, which alters the speed difference and the critical gap threshold. This traffic condition is very prevalent in almost all developed countries and leads to no lane.

T3: Road Safety. [R2-2]The vehicle-pedestrian interaction influences driving behavior with the safety of the primary concern [43–45]. This fact is also related to operational traffic safety and accidents in geometric elements of urban roundabouts.

T4: Individual Driving Behavior Modeling. [R2-2]Lane change, vehicle interaction, road vehicle trajectory are all common insights for a driving behavior out of which the frequency of lane change and volume are crucial to study [47–50].

Driving is subjected to various alteration dynamics that deals with the principles of longitudinal and lateral motions [55, 56]. A theory of consensus in ABS studies the analysis of longitudinal control and reward function.

[R2-2]Acceleration and deceleration patterns and determining speed characteristics help to make decisions about driver behavior and speed of vehicles [51, 52, 57].

Most of the practicality of driving behavior patterns comes into play during uncontrolled intersections, roundabouts, and signalizations. The scientific literature suggests binary Logit left turn gap acceptance, clearing behavior approach, and gap acceptance decision as some of the recommendations [46, 53, 54].

T5: Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS). This concept along with the following behavior of the vehicle using automated driving systems with the acceptance theory of gaps with the concept of gray system theory, explains the role of the vehicle preceding the first path of the host vehicle by remarking on the car following correlative degree. [58–60]

It is important to note that some of these topics, such as road safety, traffic flow, and driver behavior, are crucial for developing countries, where road safety is a major concern and traffic flow is often not optimized due to inadequate infrastructure. Therefore, research in these areas can help improve transportation systems in developing countries and reduce the number of accidents on the roads. Some articles cover more

than one topic and were marked as exceptional cases. To normalize the weights given by each article to the research topics distribution, the most predominant topic has been labeled the head topic for which the other aspects and concepts are covered under them.

3.1.2 Application Domains

RQ3 covers not only research topics, but also the use of behavior models and simulation techniques in transportation applications. This refers to applied research, where scientific studies aim to solve practical problems in specific areas. Table 3 displays the number of articles per application domain. It should be noted that several articles address multiple domains, so the most prevalent domain per article was selected to standardize the loads assigned to each domain. The resulting application domains are urban and rural roads, metropolitan regions, roads, behavioral interventions, intelligent transport systems, and road network planning.

[R3-6]

Table 3 The reviewed articles per application domain

Application Domains	Articles	Percentage
D1 - Urban and Rural Roads	[31, 37, 40, 46, 49, 57]	20%
D2 - Metropolitan Region	[34, 39, 42, 51, 53–55]	23.4%
D3 - Highways	[32, 38, 50, 56]	13.3%
D4 - Behavioral Interventions	[35, 44, 47, 52, 59]	16.7%
D5 - Intelligent Transport Systems	[41, 48, 58, 60]	13.3%
D6 - Road Network Planning	[33, 36, 43, 45]	13.3%

D1: Urban and Rural Roads. [R2-2]The study author discovered that many authors provided a strong reason to investigate concepts that support the function of the urban and rural roads. Interesting highlights include handling unsignalized convergences, adjusting acceleration/deceleration models for more accurate speed profiles, using microsimulation and mathematical modeling to improve intersection capacity, left-turn gap recognition in uncontrolled intersections, maintaining gap values between vehicles on single-lane country roads, and collecting vehicle data during on-road driving to study real-world traffic interactions. This domain includes six articles and constitutes 20% of the total articles reviewed. Articles in this domain focus on modeling traffic networks and heterogeneous traffic flow on urban and rural roads, as well as road safety.

D2: Metropolitan Region. [R2-2]The articles that discussed threats to urban and arterial roads covered relevant ideologies. Interesting highlights include: addressing Braess paradox in traffic networks, modeling mixed traffic conditions for developing countries, addressing aggressive drivers at T intersections, developing microsimulation models for Bangkok intersections, using signalization options to improve traffic flow in Ghana, recommending VISSIM for analyzing heterogeneous traffic in India with some adjustments, and using the proposed model to build simulators like SUMO, SiMTraM, and HETEROSIM. This domain has five

articles, representing 23% of the total articles reviewed. Articles in this domain focus on traffic flow, individual driving behavior, and road safety in metropolitan regions.

- D3: Highways.** [R2-2] Many articles describe roads as a chaotic environment in which each driver tries to maintain his own comfort. To address this problem and find efficient strategies, concepts such as recognizing speed-density relationships, distinguishing systems to accurately assess capacity for Indian highways, applying stochastic models for impact-free speed control, and maintaining distance between vehicles to prevent crashes have been proposed. This domain includes four articles, representing 13% of the total articles reviewed. Articles in this domain focus on modeling the traffic network, traffic flow, and vehicle speed on highways.
- D4: Behavioral Interventions.** [R2-2] The researcher has identified potential areas for future studies to improve road transportation through behavioral interventions, including the capture of car follower behavior for the prediction of accidents, the treatment of road safety and habitual driver behavior in African countries and their sociopsychological effects, tailoring interventions for young drivers in Egypt, teaching road users to focus on speed and distance through pedestrian behavior studies, and investigating human factors that influence merging behaviors through focus group studies. This domain has five articles and represents 17% of the total articles reviewed. Articles in this domain focus on individual driving behavior and the effects of various interventions, such as advanced driver assistance systems (ADAS), on driving behavior.
- D5: Intelligent Transport Systems.** Research articles focused on promoting the principles of Intelligent Transport Systems, with highlights including: (a) Using ITS to address social problems such as congestion, traffic safety, and air pollution through Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS); (b) Considering the particle filter approach as a promising tool for developing ATIS applications; (c) Extracting lane change segments from driving sequences by modeling and recognizing patterns in steering angle through large-scale on-road data collection and processing; (d) Conducting multilane behavior analysis to benefit ADAS adaptability and acceptance by drivers. [R2-2] This domain includes four articles, which constitute 13 of the total articles reviewed. Articles in this domain focus on the use of intelligent transport systems (ITS) to improve traffic flow, safety, and efficiency.
- D6: Road Network Planning.** [R2-2] To assess the maturity of the road environment, planning and transport networks are discussed to adapt to the future settings. The researcher observes the following highlights: (a) Dynamic traffic assignment to calculate travel time. (b) Optimizing geometry, TE, and TS for unsignalized single-lane urban roundabouts to help policy makers, civil and traffic engineers. (c) Designing multilane roundabouts to address transportation problems using microsimulation for real-world case studies. (d) Extracting risk indicators to predict the likelihood of an accident using a high-resolution, spatially explicit, dynamic agent-based simulation model. This methodology can assist transportation designers in understanding how road facilities or installation

features can affect road user safety. This domain has four articles and represents 13% of the total articles reviewed. The articles in this domain are focused on road network planning and design, as well as traffic network modeling.

[R2-2] Most of the articles (23.3%) focus on the application domain of metropolitan regions. This is not surprising, as urban areas are more likely to face traffic congestion and related problems, which require effective management and planning. Urban and rural roads are the second most common application domain, accounting for 20% of the articles. This highlights the importance of addressing traffic-related challenges in both urban and rural areas. Highways and road network planning are also significant application domains, accounting for 13.3% each. [R2-2] These domains are important because highways are major corridors for transportation and road network planning is crucial for designing efficient transportation networks. Behavioral interventions and intelligent transport systems are also important application domains, accounting for 16.7% and 13.3% of the articles, respectively. These domains address the human element of traffic management and the use of technology to improve traffic flow. [R2-2] The distribution of articles in the different application domains suggests a well-rounded approach to traffic management, paying attention to urban and rural areas, highways, road network planning, behavior interventions, and intelligent transport systems.

3.2 What are the existing driver models that represent the behaviors of the drivers in developing countries? (RQ2)

Driving behavior models are based on road traffic conditions which vary depending on the country. [R2-4 5][R3-6] Several models were proposed in the literature to reproduce driving behaviors. Models may consider homogeneous or heterogeneous entities in the model, such as light vehicles, heavy vehicles, bikes, etc. Models also focus on the two major motions for driving: the longitudinal behavior, which consists of deciding the acceleration or speed to be applied according to external conditions, and the lateral behavior, which is used for controlling the position of the vehicle on the road width or when changing lane. Table 4 provides a summary of the articles reviewed on the models used and their categories. The different types of models have been classified by Arkatkar [41] and shown in Figure 6. Basically, driving behavior is divided into two families: (i) longitudinal models (or car-following models) that enables to compute the acceleration to apply to a vehicle according to a specific driving behavior. (ii) lateral control or lane changing models that enables one to simulate or control the left-right motion of the vehicle on the roads.

[R2-4 5][R3-6] The articles in Table 4 cover various aspects of traffic analysis and simulation. Among them, the Highway Capacity Manual (HCM) method is applied in seven articles. Siva et al. [31] highlight the importance of unsigned intersections in urban and rural settings. The article introduces the conflict technique, a pragmatic approach to analyzing unsigned intersections under mixed traffic conditions, providing a methodology to calculate the capacity of intersections. The proposed approach is applied in the Visakhapatnam region, India, comparing the results obtained from the proposed technique with the 2000 HCM [31]. Recognizing global heterogeneities in traffic conditions, [32] emphasize the need for region-specific methodologies, leading to the development of the Indian Highway Capacity Manual (Indo-HCM). Furthermore,

[R2-4 5][R3-6]

Table 4 The reviewed articles per type of driver behavior model. “Ho” and “He” columns indicates if the articles focus on homogeneous or heterogeneous behaviors, respectively. “Lo” and “La” indicates if the articles propose a longitudinal or lateral driving behavior, respectively

Driver Model	Ho	He	Lo	La	Articles	Percentage
HCM analysis and equation-based model	✓		✓	✓	[31-33, 40, 41, 44, 47]	23.5%
Equation-based model & Signal processing	✓		✓	✓	[48, 49, 55]	10%
Wiedemann car-following model	✓		✓		[51, 52, 54]	10%
Logit mathematical model	✓		✓		[46, 53]	6.7%
Multi-criteria and simultaneous multi-objective optimization		✓	✓	✓	[43, 45]	6.7%
Agent-based model and dedicated car following	✓		✓		[34, 36]	6.7%
PARAMICS model		✓	✓		[37, 50]	6.7%
Ad hoc equation-based model		✓	✓	✓	[42]	3.3%
Ad hoc equation-based model		✓	✓		[57]	3.3%
Ad hoc equation-based model		✓		✓	[59]	3.3%
Markov model for car following	✓		✓		[35]	3.3%
GIPPS car following model	✓		✓		[38]	3.3%
Optimal velocity robust car-following model	✓		✓		[56]	3.3%
Task-Capability-Interface model	✓		✓		[58]	3.3%
Grey System Theory	✓		✓		[60]	3.3%
Signal processing from LIDAR dataset	✓			✓	[48]	3.3%

Giuffrè et al. [33] and Jima [44] explore the estimation of the equivalents of passenger cars for heavy vehicles at single-lane roundabouts, highlighting the importance of an accurate estimate of capacity and level of service. The role of free-flow speed in assessing the Level of Service (LOS) for two-lane highways is explored, with a focus on examining methodologies under heterogeneous traffic conditions in India [40]. The study introduces a novel measure, the speed difference, and identifies the critical gap threshold value of 10 seconds as suitable for calculating the free flow speed under such conditions [40, 41]. Furthermore, the article discusses a comprehensive cross-sectional study involving nonprofessional drivers in South Egypt, with the objective of evaluating driver behavior using the Arabic version of the Driver Behavior Questionnaire [47]. [47] underscore the importance of region-specific methodologies, the development of tools such as Indo-HCM, and the consideration of heterogeneous traffic conditions in improving the precision of traffic analysis and simulation studies.

[R2-4 5][R3-6]The two-part article [48, 49] focuses on studying lane change behaviors at the tactical level from an on-road perspective, with a particular emphasis on

Fig. 6 [R2-4 5] [R3-6] Types of simulation models of the individual driving behavior that are used in developing country applications [41]

analyzing interactions between an ego vehicle and surrounding vehicles during the lane change procedure [48, 49]. Part I focuses primarily on vehicle trajectory collection, while Part II delves into lane change extraction and scene-based behavioral analysis. The paper introduces a novel system to collect vehicle trajectory on the road, using an instrumented vehicle equipped with multiple horizontal 2-D lidars that provide 360-degree coverage. The software is developed to fit laser points from all lidars onto a vehicle model, ensuring accurate state estimations of occluded data and robust data association in multiviewpoint sensing. Extensive investigations validate the performance of the system, resulting in a large set of trajectory developed during road driving in Beijing, covering a total distance of 64 km with more than 5,700 environmental trajectories. The system is the first of its kind to automatically collect all-around vehicle trajectories during road driving, demonstrating high-quality performance for studies of driving behavior from an on-road perspective, addressing vehicle interactions in real-world traffic at the trajectory level [48, 49]. In a related context, another paper [55] introduces a new model for traffic on broad roads where drivers do not strictly adhere to the lane discipline. The model considers both longitudinal and lateral motions, assuming that driver reactions are influenced by surrounding vehicles, obstacles, and unmodeled entities in visibility cones. The network of influences is represented by “influence graphs”, and in congested traffic, a time-invariant influence structure leads to homogeneous driver behavior, resulting in a layered formation with fixed distances between vehicles. In sparse and heterogeneous traffic, the velocity and

inter-vehicle separations in the modeled vehicles are uniformly bounded. Experimental verification of the model is conducted using videos of typical traffic in Mumbai city, India, recorded and processed using image processing techniques. The proposed model accurately predicts complex maneuvers, such as overtaking, sideways movements, and collision avoidance, demonstrating its applicability to real-world traffic scenarios [55].

[R2-4 5][R3-6]Three articles use the Wiedemann car following model [51, 52, 54]. They highlight the growing motorization on highways in India, mainly with 2-wheeler and 3-wheeler vehicles, which has negatively impacted both bus and car transport [51, 52, 54]. This surge in motorization has led to highly heterogeneous traffic conditions, characterized by diverse static and dynamic features of different vehicle types. Given the complexity of the system, the text emphasizes the necessity for a microscopic simulation model to analyze these conditions effectively. It notes that stochastic models, with their inherent randomness, offer superior quality compared to deterministic models. The microscopic nature of traffic simulation is particularly advantageous as it captures the psychophysical behavior of vehicular interaction. VANET model is introduced in the VISSM traffic simulator as a tool to understand the nature of mixed traffic through discrete, stochastic, and time-step-based analysis. In summary, the work underscores the importance of using traffic simulation, particularly VISSM, to gain insight into the dynamics of mixed traffic in India, using a discrete and stochastic approach for time-step-based analysis [51, 52, 54].

[R2-4 5][R3-6]Serag [46] focus on accepting left-turn gap in developing countries in the form of a binary logit left-turn gap acceptance model based on field observations 1,496 in Egypt. The study distinguishes between gap and lag, identifying influencing factors such as gap type, time interval, driver time to turn, and oncoming driver yielding behavior. Equations are developed and applied to estimate critical gaps and lags for different scenarios, revealing values lower than those of developed countries, indicating riskier driver behavior in developing countries Serag [46]. Gap acceptance at T-Intersections in India is studied by Dutta and Ahmed [53]. They focus on uncontrolled T intersections in the North-East region of India, analyzing and modeling the acceptance behavior of gaps of minor street drivers. The results indicate aggressive behavior, not only due to waiting times, but also to a lack of respect for traffic rules. Binary logit models are developed considering factors such as the duration of the gap, the clearing time, and the aggressivity of the driver. Critical gaps are estimated for aggressive and non-aggressive drivers, emphasizing the importance of considering clearing time and driver behavior in critical gap calculations [53]. Thunig and Nagel [34] address Braess's paradox in the agent-based transport simulation MATSim, distinguishing between scenarios with and without spill back effects. The study observes two types of paradox and emphasizes the importance of capturing spill-back effects for realistic modeling. Furthermore, the integration of activity-based models with dynamic traffic assignment is explored, with adjustments made to enhance the performance of MATSim, exemplified using the city of Baoding, China [34, 36]. Ochungo [37] explain the steps in the design process of the decongestion of the interchange "GSU" in Nairobi, Kenya. The design process involves microsimulation modeling using PARAMICS and AutoCAD Civil 3D geometric modeling techniques. The paper outlines the workflow steps that led to the final choice of the interchange configuration's shape and form,

emphasizing the efficacy of microsimulation models in supporting geometric remodeling for enhanced capacity and flow [37]. Al-Jameel and Kadhim [50] focus on rural roads in Iraq, with the aim of enriching the area of developing road simulation models calibrated with field data. The objectives include investigating driver behavior, developing a simulation model and calibrating it graphically and statistically with field data. The developed model is compared with the well-known S-Paramics model, demonstrating greater precision in representing driver behavior on Iraqi rural roads [50].

[R2-4 5][R3-6]The rest of the studies improve our understanding of traffic behavior, developing models for simulation and optimization, and addressing specific challenges in various traffic scenarios. Bayomy and Gomaa [35] introduces a model that incorporates a stochastic Markov regime switching model to estimate individual driver characteristics and extract different characteristics of the driving regime. The proposed model considers trajectory data such as velocity, acceleration, space gap, and switching features, allowing classification of normal and rare car following events. It has applications in crash prediction and driver assistance systems. Maurya and Budhkar [38] address the chaotic nature of Indian traffic, characterized by various types of vehicles and lack of discipline in the lane. An attempt is made to quantify the heterogeneity parameters for Indian traffic in existing car-following models, creating a modified model. The developed simulation model is used to replicate Indian traffic conditions, demonstrating a satisfactory real-time simulation of traffic characteristics in Delhi [38]. Morita et al. [42] presents a microsimulation model for mixed traffic conditions in Bangkok, Thailand. The model considers the traffic volume, geometric structure, signal control, and driving behavior parameters obtained by video observation. Sensitivity analysis explores various measures of traffic jams, highlighting the importance of combining measures to effectively reduce congestion [42]. Papathanasopoulou and Antoniou [39] focus on modeling driving maneuvers in a mixed traffic scenario in developing countries. The methodology, based on data-driven models, simplifies the modeling of longitudinal and lateral movements. The study explores the identification of significant lateral changes, particularly in situations of lane change [39]. Waizman et al. [43] and Pilko et al. [45] propose a multiobjective optimization model for single-lane urban roundabouts, with the aim of simultaneously optimizing geometry, traffic efficiency, and safety. The model uses an analytic hierarchy process for evaluation and classification. Preliminary validation identifies an optimal geometric alternative that improves traffic efficiency and safety [43, 45]. Messaoudi [56] propose an optimal velocity robust car-following model (OV-RCFM) considering control uncertainty. The objective of the model is to produce reliable and collision-free velocity control in uncertain simulation environments, contributing to the development of intelligent transportation systems [56]. Altamira et al. [57] investigate the acceleration / deceleration patterns of light vehicles on rural roads in Argentina. Using GPS logger and camera data, the study explores patterns on approach tangents, along horizontal curves, and on exit tangents. The results show variability in the rates depending on factors such as tangent length, curve radius, and longitudinal slope [57]. Hoogendoorn et al. [58] introduce a theoretical framework that integrates

the Task-Capability-Interface model into the Intelligent Driver Model to model adaptation effects in longitudinal driving behavior after driver distraction. Simulations demonstrate the suitability of the framework in describing the effects of distraction [58]. Li et al. [59] address the complexity of vehicle merging, focusing on merging position selection behavior and heterogeneity among merging drivers. A finite mixture of linear regression models is developed to describe the selection of merged positions, taking into account both lateral and longitudinal factors. The model identifies driver heterogeneity and improves accuracy in microscopic traffic simulation [59]. Yu and Wang [60] introduce Grey System Theory to analyze car-following behavior in multi-lane driving. The method establishes differences between following a host-lane vehicle and an adjacent-lane vehicle, emphasizing the need to explore drivers' behavior rules in multilane driving for advanced driver assistance systems [60].

The answer to RQ2 describes various models used for traffic management and decongestion processes in different countries. The models vary in their level of sophistication, incorporating factors such as vehicle heterogeneity, lateral interaction, and road geometry. The use of microsimulation models is highlighted for decongestion design processes in African countries, where road conditions are heterogeneous. Discrete choice models are used for pedestrian interaction with vehicles, but do not represent events that occur after pedestrians or drivers make a decision. Finally, the passage concludes that car follow-up models that support gap acceptance behavior should be given high priority for consideration when using a suitable ANS approach, but the model is limited to countries driving on the left-hand side.

3.3 What are the suitable models for agent-oriented simulation of driving behavior in developing countries, and how can it be implemented into an agent-oriented simulator? (RQ3)

The answer to this RQ is structured in two subsections dedicated to the two parts of the questions.

3.3.1 ABS models for driver behavior in developing countries

The rapid increase in heterogeneous traffic conditions poses challenges to lane analysis and car follow models, especially in locations with poor lane management or deteriorating flow patterns. Researchers have used traffic simulation frameworks to develop better driver behavior models [61] and gain insight into driver behavior [62, 63].

[R2-4 5][R3-6]Table 5 synthesizes the articles that contribute in the field of agent-based modeling (ABM). However, a large part of the selected articles (66.7%) do not contribute explicitly in ABM, depicting the fact that agent-based microsimulation is one of the major approaches in the field of traffic simulation since a decade, as illustrated by the number of related articles in the last column of Table 5.

- (i) **ABM for longitudinal and lateral driving behavior:** [R2-4 5][R3-6]The majority of the proposed models focus on the longitudinal behavior of the drivers. They are deterministic models that ensure collision-free speed control [72]. Among the most commonly used ABM models, the Wiedemann [73] model (on the VISSIM platform), the Gipps [74] model (on the MATSIM platform), and

[R2-4 5][R3-6]

Table 5 The reviewed articles per type of agent-based model for reproducing driving behaviors

ABM Driving Model	Articles	Percentage	Related Articles
Wiedemann / VISSIM	[51, 52, 54]	10%	[64, 65]
Gipps / MATSIM	[34, 36, 38]	10%	[39, 64, 66–71]
PARAMICS	[37, 50]	6.7%	[64, 71]
Data-driven or activity-based model	[39]	3.3%	[68–70]
Optimal velocity robust car-following model	[56]	3.3%	
No specific ABM	[31–33, 35, 40–49, 53, 55, 57–60]	66.7%	

PARAMICS could be observed in the reviewed articles. They are used to model the behavior of individual vehicles using a car follow model and a lane change model [75].

[R2-4 5][R3-6] According to Mehar et al. [64], Wiedemann [73] model cannot reproduce mixed traffic conditions that affect Indian roads. On the contrary, the Gipps [74] model has shown potential for better field condition replication than other models in unstable states. However, lane-based models are not always applicable in heterogeneous traffic conditions prevalent in developing countries [64].

[R2-4 5][R3-6] Many examples of the use of ABM with MATSim or VISSIM for the modeling and the simulation of driving behavior in developing countries could be found in articles that are outside the selection criteria of this study [36, 39, 64, 66–70].

- (ii) **Activity-based models in conjunction with ABM:** Data-driven approaches, such as activity-based models, have shown promise in providing flexible car follower models and a more reliable representation of driving behavior [39].
- (iii) **Dynamic Traffic Assignment in conjunction with ABM:** [R2-4 5][R3-6] When coupled with dynamic traffic assignment, ABM can help account for the impact of traffic conditions on individual travel behavior, such as location of activity and route choice. Although the simplified Gipps [74] model generally has weak parts related to ABM, it can potentially become a fully integrated ABM and DTA structure capable of modeling traffic-based travel demand and simultaneously adjusting activity types, locations, and sequence.

For answering RQ3, the existing models of individual driving behaviors discussed previously are suitable for ABS. ABS involves modeling the behavior of individual agents, such as drivers, and their interactions within a larger system. The driving behavior models, such as the Wiedemann [73] or Gipps [74] models, are designed to capture the behavior of individual drivers in different situations and can be used to simulate their actions and interactions within a larger traffic system.

[R2-4 5][R3-6] In fact, many ABS frameworks, such as MATSIM or VISSIM (as well as two other major traffic simulation frameworks: SUMO and GAMA) already

incorporate these driving behavior models to simulate individual driver behavior and interactions. Various applications have been developed, such as Treiterer [76] and Wu et al. [77]. However, several works such as [78, 79] have relied on ad hoc rules to model the traffic of developing countries without sustainable numerical properties, leading to limitations in the reliability of the simulated directions. To address this problem, a more comprehensive and numerically rigorous model is necessary and was studied in different research works [23, 76–84].

[R2-4 5][R3-6]Furthermore, the problem of pedestrian-vehicle interaction in developing countries is a concern [43]. Waizman et al. [85] propose a dynamic agent-based simulation model (named SAFEPEP) to model and simulate the discrete choice of drivers and pedestrians and assess accident risks [43]. Solving the conflicts among drivers and pedestrians is based on the Gibson hypothesis of affordance [86]. Moreover, Braess’s paradox is a phenomenon that states that, by adding a link to the network, there can be an increase in the total travel time of a user equilibrium [87, 88]. It can be simulated using MATSIM with time-dependent travel times. The inquiry whether a situation contains Braess’s paradox is complex, and finding a mechanism to identify Braess links, such as links that should be removed, is much harder [71].

3.3.2 Key properties of the individual behavior models

According to Rossi et al. [89], Kim et al. [90], computer simulations have the potential to overcome some of the limitations of transport field studies. However, the precision of the simulations depends on the precise modeling of vehicle components and driver behavior, especially during critical maneuvers [91]. An accurate and reliable reproduction of driving behavior is essential to create a realistic microscopic simulation of urban traffic [92]. The following properties are critical for this purpose:

- Traveled distance for every movement in each approach;
- Times of arrival and departure on reference lines for every vehicle from each stream;
- Approach speed of the vehicles;
- Volume at unsignalized intersection development insightful.

[R2-2]The study found that traffic flow in western countries is characteristically variable with marginal variation, contrary to the large variation found on the roads of developing countries [31].

Another important factor to consider is the driver’s speed profile, which can aid in critical analysis. Speed profiles describe the operating speed of vehicles on highways and are used to estimate fuel consumption, exhaust emissions, operating costs, and travel time, and to perform a consistency evaluation of the mathematical design of the road. Speed profiles are generated using mathematical models for speed calculation and acceleration. Speed calculation is widely studied in the literature, and it is a historical fact that on level curves, the radius of the curve and the speed at the approaching tangent are the main factors that explain the operating velocities [93–96]. Additionally, acceleration models are necessary to describe the speed profiles when passing through curves to/from straight-tangent changes. A power analysis through linear regression or algorithm models such as ANOVA would usually help to achieve this purpose.

The behavior of car following varies according to the driving situation and can be divided into five regimes: (i) acceleration, (ii) approaching, (iii) braking, (iv) stable following, and (v) free flow. The driver's behavior in each regime changes depending on the driving situation. The approaching situation starts when the following vehicle becomes close to the lead vehicle and ends when the following vehicle reaches the desired safe distance of stable follow. In the case of a slowing situation, the following vehicle becomes too close and is faster than the lead vehicle, so the follower decelerates slightly [35].

[R2-2]The acceptance behavior of the gap is influenced not only by intersection characteristics, vehicular characteristics, opposing flow and type of control, but also by subjective elements such as the mental and *socioeconomic status of the drivers, weather conditions, asphalt and light conditions, and vehicle occupancy* [53, 97–102].

Drivers were found to *behave aggressively* due to their disregard of traffic rules rather than being upset by the inaccessibility of a suitable gap. *Age* also plays an important role in the decision-making process for gap acceptance, with adults making better decisions than older children, who make better decisions than younger children. Gap assessment involves making judgments about whether it is possible to complete a maneuver before an oncoming vehicle arrives and requires considering both the distance and speed of the approaching vehicle.

3.4 What kind of driving environment is considered having identified the driver behaviours? (RQ4)

Agent-based simulations, when implemented with driving models, can adapt to these environmental attributes [103]. [R2-2]The heterogeneity of entities and infrastructures is an essential aspect of traffic modeling and simulation, and it is important to develop models that can accurately capture these characteristics to improve traffic flow and safety in developing countries.

3.4.1 Heterogeneity of entities

Heterogeneous traffic in India comprises buses, trucks, light commercial vehicles, cars, three-wheelers, two-wheelers, bicycles and tricycles [104]. [R2-2]Dynamic traffic models have been developed for Indian conditions, where lane discipline is rarely observed, and the distances between vehicles can vary significantly [55]. These models take into account differences in vehicle characteristics, road user behavior patterns, and traffic flow patterns, and can provide a more realistic representation of traffic dynamics on Indian roads.

3.4.2 Heterogeneity of infrastructures

Each developing country has a unique driving environment characterized by factors such as unsignalized intersections, increased roundabouts, heterogeneous traffic conditions, traffic demand, geometric restrictions of the road, road elements, and behavior patterns of road users. Researchers initially focused on traffic control and limits in the road network, but efforts have been made to improve flow efficiency [105, 106]. The development of traffic light planning is a commonly used method, but microsimulation

[R2-6]

Table 6 Relationship between the initial research questions (RQ) and the synthesized major research directions (RD)

Research Questions	Research Directions
RQ1 - What are the research topics and application domains of the articles related to the topics of this study?	This RQ does not lead to a specific RD. Answering this question increases the general knowledge of the reader.
RQ2 - What are the existing driver models that represent the behaviors of the drivers in developing countries?	RD1 - Heterogeneity of traffic entities; RD2 - Dynamic and Virtualized Structure of Roads
RQ3 - What are the suitable models for agent-oriented simulation of driving behavior in developing countries, and how can it be implemented into an agent-oriented simulator?	RD1 - Heterogeneity of traffic entities; RD2 - Dynamic and Virtualized Structure of Roads
RQ4 - What kind of driving environment is considered having identified the driver behaviours?	RD2 - Dynamic and Virtualized Structure of Roads; RD3 - Optimal Infrastructure Design

models do not explicitly yield a limit as a performance measure [107]. Delays at intersections are classified into several types and roundabouts are common bottlenecks on metro routes [108]. Computational configurations for traffic analysis generally cannot model irregular configurations [109, 110].

[R2-2] Various models to determine roundabout capacity under mixed traffic conditions suggest that it is strongly influenced by mathematical factors [111]. Research on roundabouts in different countries, especially single-lane roundabouts (signalized and unsigned) in urban areas, has shown that proper design and modeling can significantly improve traffic efficiency (TE) [112–116] and traffic safety (TS) [117–119]. However, these and other studies [120–122] have shown that current design and modeling guidelines are not always suitable for situations that require simultaneous optimization of calculations, TE, and TS. Interestingly, many countries in Africa and Asia still construct numerous roundabouts for their highway sectors, but often overlook the beneficial characteristics of roundabouts, as these structures have a unique set of design requirements that must be adapted to each road environment [123].

Geometrical factors such as the circle radii, the entry/exit radii, the entry/exit approach width and the direction of the vehicle path have been improved [124], while the link between the speed of the vehicle path configuration through the roundabout and the observed vehicle speeds has been studied.

4 Challenges and Research Directions

[R2-6] In this section, the main challenges and research directions related to the driving model in developing countries are listed. These research directions are mentioned in articles in the reviewed literature or identified based on the own experiences of the authors of this article. All the research directions and work perspectives found have been synthesized in three major research directions that are related to the initial RQ, as illustrated by Table 6.

4.1 RD1: Heterogeneity of traffic entities

Modeling heterogeneous traffic, which includes vehicles such as 2- or 3-wheelers, trucks, and pedestrians, is not completely accurate at the macroscopic and microscopic levels. Empirical evidence indicates that drivers exhibit varied responses when encountering different types of vehicle, particularly in scenarios such as narrow roads or roundabouts, where the geometry of the road affects vehicles differently depending on their maneuverability.

Due to the significant heterogeneity and unique driver behavior on Indian roads, which differs from other developing countries such as China and Indonesia, the principles developed for other countries cannot be easily applied to Indian traffic conditions without establishing suitable adjustment factors. Recognizing this information gap, the CSIR Central Road Research Institute has undertaken the Indonesian HCM project to develop a road capacity manual specifically for Indian conditions, covering the full range of road facilities available in the country [32]. [R2-2]Indonesian HCM considers the heterogeneous traffic conditions commonly found on Indonesian roads. It defines the base conditions for its multipath highways differently, including 3.5 m traffic path or lane widths, shoulders of an effective width of 1.0 m for each road, a divided road, flat terrain, no roadside improvements, very low side grinding, functional class of the road as arterial street and more than 70% of the segment with a view distance greater than 300 meters. However, the Indonesian HCM takes into account certain roadside events in the section, such as the presence of pedestrians, stops made by public transport and other vehicles, vehicles entering and leaving roadside premises, and slow moving vehicles, while limiting the weighted frequency of such events to less than 50. Furthermore, the Indonesian HCM specifies the sight distance requirements, which are not included in the US-HCM, considering local conditions [32].

In the real world, the stochastic environment of vehicle control actions can result in control uncertainty, mainly due to tire slip and brake lock-up. Applying the same acceleration at the same speed could lead to different and often unpredictable outcomes. Consequently, drivers can become uncertain about the specific result of their actions, leading to control uncertainty [72].

[R2-2][R1-4]Among the types of entity that could be found in a traffic system, the autonomous vehicle (AV) has a particular position. In fact, the arrival of AV may constitute another significant turning point in the development of our daily lives, the urban environment, and human civilization as a whole. An extremely disruptive technology, whose use will affect parking problems, air pollution, travel habits, road safety, and other elements of daily life. In developed countries, autonomous vehicles are expected to be widely used for daily transportation in the next ten years. Developing countries would not be able to implement it for at least another fifty years [125]. However, it might soon be used in specific applications [125].

[R2-2][R1-4]The recent study undertaken by Kumar et al. [125] cites the main research directions that researchers could consider. One of them is related to cybersecurity risks. It constitutes one of the main barriers to the adoption of self-driving vehicles, including in developing countries. This study may help explain the interdependence of obstacles for organizations and countries that try to promote the use of autonomous vehicles in developing countries. A policy for autonomous vehicle research

must be developed in conjunction with standard testing and homologation procedures. Adopting a legislative framework and uniform safety standards is also necessary for organizations and nations. Developing countries must embrace a methodical approach to planning, implementing, and maintaining autonomous vehicles to win consumers' trust and alleviate concerns about their safety. In a similar approach to the one in this article, Kumar et al. [125] highlight the main obstacles to the general public's acceptance of autonomous vehicles, but it does not provide a numerical estimate of how these obstacles will affect the stated goal. Furthermore, the approach has not been statistically tested and is dependent on professional judgment.

4.2 RD2: Dynamic and Virtualized Structure of Roads

In certain developing countries, such as India, a common feature is the lack of strong lane discipline, resulting in vehicles often straddling between lanes. Empirical evidence has shown that this results in an increase in road capacity but a decrease in speed profile. Although this phenomenon can be incorporated into macroscopic simulation models through certain adjustments, ongoing research is attempting to model its implications at the microscopic level, such as in trajectory planning and car-following speed adaptation. To advance these studies, an integrated model is necessary, together with further comparisons with field data from different countries.

[R3-6]Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) offer considerable potential to change driving behaviors. Their effectiveness is compromised when drivers prone to risky behavior persist in engaging in distracting activities. Although real-time warnings have been shown to improve driving behavior, the sustained impact of warning-based ADAS on curbing driving distractions among light commercial vehicle (LCV) drivers remains uncertain [126]. The findings indicate that warning-based ADAS, which provides real-time alerts, effectively reduces distraction events that lead to driver inattention, forward collisions, and lane departures. The research reveals that passive and active monitoring systems, when combined with coaching and rewards, significantly reduce aggressive driving behaviors related to harsh acceleration (by 76%) and harsh braking (by 65%) [126]. These research results offer valuable support to road safety stakeholders in developing countries, helping them develop risk assessments based on warning-based ADAS, launch targeted campaigns to reduce driving distractions, and implement effective driving coaching programs.

[R3-6]In countries such as India, numerous road projects have been implemented to facilitate travel and connectivity throughout the country. However, HCM expectations for commercial roads, where lanes are maintained, but road users do not necessarily follow the lane-following pattern, may not always promise the implementation of a good leader-follower model. One such project in India is Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana (PMGSY), which was started in 2000 to connect rural areas with other major roads such as NH and SH to provide easy access for residents to sell and purchase their goods. The project has also improved the standard of living of people by making them more accessible to NH and SH. PMGSY covers the streets of different areas (ODR) and town streets (VR) that have a single path street for two-way traffic, playing a crucial role in connecting rural areas to market communities, the base camp of Taluka, the improvement center of the block, or other primary roads [40]. Although several

studies have examined the performance of different roads, such as NH and SH, in terms of service level (LOS), no such examination has been carried out for single-path roads [40]. A road is considered to have good LOS when vehicles travel at their optimal speed or in free flow conditions (FFC), which refers to the condition in which vehicles travel at their ideal speed without being influenced by other vehicle classifications in the same traffic flow [40]. Studies presume that a vehicle should travel in free flow conditions if its speed is not affected by any other vehicle in the traffic flow [40].

4.3 RD3: Optimal Infrastructure Design

Efficient models that estimate the capacity of current and future road infrastructure in developing countries do not address the question of optimal design of such infrastructure. To address this gap, ongoing research is focused on determining the ideal infrastructure configuration in terms of routes, geometry, and signage, while taking into account the unique characteristics of developing countries, such as specific driver behaviors, heterogeneous traffic, and an existing infrastructure that contains many roundabouts and unsignalized intersections.

Investing in technology and infrastructure for the transportation industry requires considering various factors. Developing countries face challenges due to the lack of categorization of land parcels and mixed land use. This leads to the need for new or modified road sections and the interference of heavy and light vehicles on urban roads. [R1-4]This point of view is shared by Kumar et al. [125] and Outay et al. [17]. They highlight a major research challenge related to the requirement of cyber infrastructure. In fact, it constitutes one of the main barriers to the adoption of self-driving vehicles, especially in developing countries. These changes affect (self) driving behavior and can lead to longer commutes and a dangerous impact on drivers.

[R2-2][R1-4]This research study emphasizes the need to understand the land parcels, comply with the required road standards, and consider the environmental impacts and energy consumption. Researchers should focus on the patterns of following new cars to address the impact of these changes on drivers.

[R2-2][R1-4]Some researchers try to overcome the problem of the existence of a cyber infrastructure by allowing vehicles, and especially autonomous vehicles, to interact directly without information from the cyber infrastructure. For example, [127] considers that intersections are major bottlenecks for road traffic, as well as the source of many accidents. They propose an inter-vehicle scheduling algorithm for intersections of cooperative vehicles in order to maximize the throughput of the intersection. More specifically, they propose an approach based on deep reinforcement learning and Markov Decision Process to efficiently distribute the right-of-way to each vehicle.

5 Related Works

[R1-3]The focus of this research is specific. However, several articles have been published, which provides survey articles related to the topics of this article. This section provides a brief overview of these secondary studies.

[R1-3] Cidjeu Djeuthie et al. [128] have conducted a short survey with research questions similar to those presented in this article. However, they have focused their

study on sub-Saharan countries, when our study has no geographical limitation. There are some similarities in the terminology used, such as the application of multiagent models for spatiotemporal dynamic growth in developing urban areas; the literature does not address the specific focus of this research [129]. For example, previous research on the modeling of driver route choice does not consider the dynamic and virtual infrastructure [130]. The latter study aims to demonstrate the ability to make environmental decisions with the support of travel information that does not align with the point of interest in this research. In the article of Bouhsissin et al. [131] and Zaidan et al. [132], the aim of the study is to highlight and analyze the different types of driver behavior, data sources, datasets, characteristics, and artificial intelligence techniques used to classify driver behavior and its performance. Both of these secondary studies do not focus on developing countries and the associated issues. Elamrani Abou Elassad et al. [133] present an SLR of the concept of driving behavior with a holistic approach to the different aspects of driving behavior analysis, as well as a scheme to guide the future development and implementation of assessment strategies. In the second part of this article, an overview of the literature on machine learning is highlighted. Saleh et al. [134] provides an SLR on the development of sustainable heritage cities in Malaysia without focusing on mobility and driving models. Among the secondary studies found by the authors, none is dedicated to agent-based modeling of traffic and drivers.

[R1-3]Regarding the SLR methodology, many secondary studies have been published using this approach. Tchappi et al. [135] have proposed an SLR study on the usage and application of holonic multiagent systems in the fields of traffic and transportation. Mualla et al. [136] have provided a very detailed survey on the modeling and application of drones in civilian applications. Mkhinini et al. [137] provides a comprehensive review of the combination of the Unified Modeling Language and ontology paradigm. Calvaresi et al. [138] were interested in the design of chatbots with an individual perspective and using the agent-oriented modeling paradigm.

6 Conclusion

In this research, the survey of behavior models for drivers in developing countries has been extensively studied, with various ideologies and concepts captured to help understand the subject matter. The study identified that driver psychosocial behavior plays an important role in altering or improving the road environment with its associated interactors. Various car follower models that are currently adopted or exist in many developing countries were discussed, evaluated, and reviewed. The report also identified various properties that must be considered to adapt a driver model, especially with unsteady traffic flows, excessive approach demand, and varying directional flows at roundabouts. The traffic operations and congestion design process adopted in certain cities in Asia and Africa were very useful to predict and determine the importance of geometric standards on roads, which can play a vital role for any driver behavior model when deployed and tested.

The model analyzes indicated that the behavior of drivers in developing countries is more hazardous, or they do not adhere somewhat to the traffic rules. Prompt suggestions based on the overall study would be to recommend the future scope of research on traffic environments in countries such as India, the Philippines, Thailand, and parts of Africa. An unprecedented scenario-based driver behavior model is already available for highly developed countries. Coverage of car following models during adverse climatic conditions would help identify potential risks and threats faced by drivers and their behavioral condition, which can become a source of information to build future concepts on Lane following models. On this note, if such an initiative takes place, the level of scope of such models can be assessed and recommended to other developing countries.

To the researcher's knowledge and awareness, no literature articles are available that summarize and capture the developing country's driving behavior models in one research study. Thus, this research work can benefit future scholars and researchers in identifying this as a basis for further extension. It is essential to note that this research study did not explicitly point out a particular driving behavior model of interest, but it captures the essence of various prevalent car following models and driver behavior models associated with developing countries.

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 - Vishal A. Gracian has completed the SLR process as a Master student. He is also the main contributor to the text of the article.

- Stéphane Galland has realized the SLR process as an expert. He is also the second major contributor to the text of the article. He is the major contributor for the revised text of the article.
- Alexandre Lombard has performed the SLR process as an expert. He is also the third major contributor to the text of the article.
- Thomas Martinet has performed the SLR process as an expert. He is also the fourth major contributor to the text of the article.
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References

- [1] O’Sullivan, A., Sheffrin, S.M.: Economics: Principles in Action vol. 07458. Pearson Prentice Hall, ??? (2003)
- [2] Althor, G., Watson, J.E., Fuller, R.A.: Global mismatch between greenhouse gas emissions and the burden of climate change. *Scientific Reports* **6**(1) (2016) <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep20281>
- [3] Dupont, P., Egan, K.: Solving bangkok’s transport woes: The need to ask the right questions. *World Transport Policy and Practice* **3**(1), 25–37 (1997)
- [4] World Bank: Sustainable Transport: Priorities for Policy Reform
- [5] Gakenheimer, R.: Urban mobility in the developing world. *Transportation Research Part A* **33**, 671–689 (1999)
- [6] Sperling, D., Salon, D.: Transportation in Developing Countries: An Overview of Greenhouse Gas Reduction Strategies. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0cglr4nq>
- [7] World Health Organization: Global Status Report on Road Safety
- [8] Ennajih, D., Elgameh, M., Echchelh, S.A., Chaouch, A.: Study of the influence of parameters of road safety on the road accidents. *Int J Res Stud Sci Eng Technol* **2**(4), 22–27 (2015)
- [9] Kanagaraj, V., Asaithambi, G., Kumar, C.N., Srinivasan, K.K., Sivanandan, R.: Evaluation of different vehicle following models under mixed traffic conditions. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences* **104**, 390–401 (2013)
- [10] Djeddi, T., Haidouchi, A.: Determination of the main factors of road accidents in algeria during the period algeria. *Sci J Platform* **12**, 21–35 (2015)
- [11] Ahmed, D., Dahbia, D., Tebbal, L.: The reality traffic accidents in algeria. a comparative study between algeria and the arab countries and the developed

center for promoting ideas. *Int J Bus Social Sci.* **8**, 158 (2017)

- [12] Algerian national center for road safe and prevention: Decrease of traffic accidents in algeria. *Atlas Magazine* (2018)
- [13] Boufedda, E.: The main causes of road accidents in algeria. *Revue EL Bahith en Sciences Humaines et Sociales*, 113–118 (2019)
- [14] Ghaweel, I.A., Mursi, S.A., Jack, J.P., Joel, I.: Factors affecting road traffic accidents in benghazi libya. *Libyan J of Medicine* (2008)
- [15] Yahia, I.A., Hussin, A.M.: Causes and effects of road traffic accidents in tripoli libya. In: the 6th Civil Engineering Conference in Asia Region (2009)
- [16] Tayfour, A., Awadalla, G.A.: Characteristics and prediction of traffic accident casualties in sudan using statistical modeling and artificial neural networks. *Int J Transportation Sci Technol* **1**, 305–317 (2012)
- [17] Outay, F., Galland, S., Gaud, N., Abbas-Turki, A.: Simulation of connected driving in hazardous weather conditions: General and extensible multiagent architecture and models. *Int. Journal of Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence (EAAI)* **104**, 104412 (2021) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2021.104412>
- [18] Prabuchandran, K.J., Hemanth Kumar, A.N., Bhatnagar, S.: Multi-agent reinforcement learning for traffic signal control. In: 17th International IEEE Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC), pp. 2529–2534 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ITSC.2014.6958095>
- [19] Krajzewicz, D., Erdmann, J., Behrisch, M., Bieker, L.: Recent development and applications of SUMO-simulation of urban mobility. *International Journal on Advances in Systems and Measurements* **5**(3&4) (2012)
- [20] Horni, A., Nagel, K., Axhausen, K.W.: *The Multi-Agent Transport Simulation MATSim*. Ubiquity Press, London, GBR (2016)
- [21] Wooldridge, M.: *An Introduction to Multiagent Systems*. John Wiley & Sons, ??? (2009)
- [22] Weiss, G., al.: *Multiagent systems. Intelligent Robotics and Autonomous Agents* (2013)
- [23] Munigety, C.R., Mathew, T.V.: Towards behavioral modeling of drivers in mixed traffic conditions. *Transportation in Developing Economies* **2**(1), 1–20 (2016)
- [24] Budgen, D., Brereton, P.: Performing systematic literature reviews in software engineering. In: the 28th International Conference on Software Engineering, pp. 1051–1052. ACM, ??? (2006)

- [25] Kitchenham, B.A., Brereton, P., Turner, M., Niazi, M.K., Linkman, S., Pretorius, R., Budgen, D.: Refining the systematic literature review process—two participant-observer case studies. *Empir. Softw. Eng.* **15**(6), 618–653 (2010)
- [26] Kitchenham, B., Charters, S.: *Guidelines for Performing Systematic Literature Reviews in Software Engineering*
- [27] Mualla, Y., Najjar, A., Daoud, A., Galland, S., Nicolle, C., Yasar, A.-U.-H., Shakshuki, E.: Agent-based simulation of unmanned aerial vehicles in civilian applications: A systematic literature review and research directions. *Future Generation Computer Systems* **100**, 344–364 (2019) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2019.04.051> . Scimago/WOS Q-Indexes: Q1, Impact factor: 7.187
- [28] Brereton, P., Kitchenham, B.A., Budgen, D., Turner, M., Khalil, M.: Lessons from applying the systematic literature review process within the software engineering domain. *Journal of Systems and Software* **80**(4), 571–583 (2007)
- [29] Galster, M., Weyns, D., Tofan, D., Michalik, B., Avgeriou, P.: Variability in software systems - a systematic literature review. *IEEE Trans. Softw. Eng.* **40**(3), 282–306 (2014)
- [30] Calvaresi, D., Cesarini, D., Sernani, P., Marinoni, M., Dragoni, A.F., Sturm, A.: Exploring the ambient assisted living domain: a systematic review. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing* **8**(2), 239–57 (2017)
- [31] Siva, S., Prasad, G., Surisetty, R., Ch, S.: A study on gap-acceptance of unsignalized intersection under mixed traffic conditions. *Int. J. of Research in Engineering and Technology* (2014)
- [32] Arun, A., Senathipathi, V., Madhu, E.: Methodological framework towards roadway capacity estimation for indian multi-lane highways. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* **104**, 477–486 (2013) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.11.141>
- [33] Giuffrè, O., Grana, A., Tumminello, M., Sferlazza, A.: Estimation of passenger car equivalents for single-lane roundabouts using a microsimulation-based procedure. *Expert Systems with Applications* **79** (2017) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2017.03.003>
- [34] Thunig, T., Nagel, K.: Braess’s paradox in an agent-based transport model. *Procedia Computer Science* **83**, 946–951 (2016) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2016.04.190> . The 7th International Conference on Ambient Systems, Networks and Technologies (ANT 2016) / The 6th International Conference on Sustainable Energy Information Technology (SEIT-2016) / Affiliated Workshops
- [35] Bayomy, A., Gomaa, W.: Car following regime taxonomy based on markov switching. In: *Proceedings of the 17th IEEE International Conference on*

- Intelligent Transportation Systems (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ITSC.2014.6957871>
- [36] Zhuge, C., Bithell, M., Shao, C., Li, X., Gao, J.: An improvement in MATSim computing time for large-scale travel behaviour microsimulation. *Transportation* (2019) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11116-019-10048-0>
- [37] Ochungo, A.E.: Decongestion of nairobi-thika highway-outer ring road “gsu” intersection using microsimulation and geometric modeling. *American Journal of Water Resources* **8**(2), 45–55 (2020) <https://doi.org/10.12691/ajwr-8-2-1>
- [38] Maurya, A., Budhkar, A.: Development of simulation model for heterogeneous traffic with no lane discipline. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* **104**, 360–369 (2013) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.11.129>
- [39] Papathanasopoulou, V., Antoniou, C.: Flexible car-following models for mixed traffic and weak lane-discipline conditions. *European Transport Research Review* **10**(20138) (2018) <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12544-018-0338-0>
- [40] Boora, A., Ghosh, I., Chandra, S.: Identification of free flowing vehicles on two lane intercity highways under heterogeneous traffic condition. *Transportation Research Procedia* **21**, 130–140 (2017) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2017.03.083> . International Symposia of Transport Simulation (ISTS) and the International Workshop on Traffic Data Collection and its Standardization (IWTDCS)
- [41] Arkatkar, S.: Traffic operations and capacity analysis in india. *Transportation Letters* **10**, 65–67 (2018) <https://doi.org/10.1080/19427867.2017.1374007>
- [42] Morita, H., Inenaga, S., Takano, T.: Microsimulation for mixed traffic flow at intersection area in bangkok. In: 2019 First International Conference on Smart Technology Urban Development (STUD), pp. 1–6 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1109/STUD49732.2019.9018840>
- [43] Waizman, G., Shoval, S., Benenson, I.: Traffic accident risk assessment with dynamic microsimulation model using range-range rate graphs. *Accident Analysis & Prevention* **119**, 248–262 (2018) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2018.07.027>
- [44] Jima, D.: Review on factors causes road traffic accident in africa. *Journal of Civil Engineering Research & Technology* **2**, 41–49 (2019)
- [45] Pilko, H., Mandžuka, S., Barić, D.: Urban single-lane roundabouts: a new analytical approach using multi-criteria and simultaneous multi-objective optimization of geometry design, efficiency and safety. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies* **80**, 257–271 (2017) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2017.04.018>

- [46] Serag, M.: Gap-acceptance behavior at uncontrolled intersections in developing countries. *Malaysian Journal of Civil Engineering* **27**(1), 80–93 (2015)
- [47] Arafa, A., Saleh, L.H., Senosy, S.A.: Age-related differences in driving behaviors among non-professional drivers in egypt. *PLOS ONE* **15**(9), 1–9 (2020) <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0238516>
- [48] Yao, W., Zeng, Q., Lin, Y., Xu, D., Zhao, H., Guillemard, F., Geronimi, S., Aioun, F.: On-road vehicle trajectory collection and scene-based lane change analysis : Part II. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* **18**, 1–15 (2016) <https://doi.org/10.1109/TITS.2016.2571724>
- [49] Zhao, H., Wang, C., Lin, Y., Guillemard, F., Geronimi, S., Aioun, F.: On-road vehicle trajectory collection and scene-based lane change analysis: Part I. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* **18**, 1–14 (2016) <https://doi.org/10.1109/TITS.2016.2571726>
- [50] Al-Jameel, H., Kadhim, A.: Rural traffic characteristics using field data and the developed simulation model. In: *IOP Conference on Materials Science and Engineering* (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/888/1/012058>
- [51] Gupta, N.: Microscopic traffic simulation using vanets traffic simulator VISSIM. *Int. J. of Research in Engineering and Technology* **03**, 56–58 (2014) <https://doi.org/10.15623/ijret.2014.0326012>
- [52] Hunt, M., Harper, D.N., Lie, C.: Mind the gap: Training road users to use speed and distance when making gap-acceptance decisions. *Int. J. Accident, analysis and prevention* **43**, 2015–202358 (2011) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2011.05.020>
- [53] Dutta, M., Ahmed, M.: Gap acceptance behaviour of drivers at uncontrolled T-intersections under mixed traffic conditions. *Journal of Modern Transportation* **26** (2017) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40534-017-0151-9>
- [54] Kwakwa, O., Adams, C., Ackaah, W., Oliver-Commey, Y.: Signalization options to improve capacity and delay at roundabouts through microsimulation approach: A case study on arterial roadways in ghana. *Journal of Traffic and Transportation Engineering* (2019) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtte.2019.06.003>
- [55] Mulla, A., Joshi, A., Chavan, R., Chakraborty, D., Manjunath, D.: A microscopic model for lane-less traffic. *IEEE Transactions on Control of Network Systems* (2018) <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCNS.2018.2834313>
- [56] Messaoudi, O.: An optimal velocity robust car-following model with consideration of control uncertainty. In: *2018 International Conference on Applied Smart Systems (ICASS)*, pp. 1–8 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICASS.2018.8652077>

- [57] Altamira, A., García Ramírez, Y., Echaveguren, T., Marcet, J.: Acceleration and deceleration patterns on horizontal curves and their tangents on two-lane rural roads. In: Proceedings of the 93rd Annual Meeting of the Transportation Research Board (2014)
- [58] Hoogendoorn, R.G., Arem, B., Hoogendoorn, S.: Incorporating driver distraction in car-following models: Applying the TCI to the IDM. In: Proceedings of the 2013 IEEE Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems, pp. 2274–2279 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ITSC.2013.6728566>
- [59] Li, G., Pan, Y., Yang, Z., Ma, J.: Modeling vehicle merging position selection behaviors based on a finite mixture of linear regression models. *IEEE Access* (2019) <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2950444>
- [60] Yu, C., Wang, J.: Drivers' car-following correlative behavior with preceding vehicles in multilane driving. In: Proceedings of the 2014 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium, pp. 64–69 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1109/IVS.2014.6856494>
- [61] Vladislavljevic, I., Cooper, J.M., Martin, P.T., Strayer, D.L.: Importance of integrating driving and traffic simulations: case study of impact of cell phone drivers on traffic flow. In: Proceedings of 88th Annual Meeting of the Transportation Research Board, Washington D.C., USA (2009)
- [62] Farah, H., Polus, A., Bekhor, S., Toledo, T.: Study of passing gap acceptance behaviour using a driving simulator. *Adv. Transp. Stud. Int. J.*, 9–16 (2007). Special Issue
- [63] Engel, D., Curio, C.: Detectability prediction in dynamic scenes for enhanced environment perception. In: Proceedings of 2012 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ivs.2012.6232267>
- [64] Mehar, A., Chandra, S., Velmurugan, S.: Highway capacity through vissim calibrated for mixed traffic conditions. *KSCE Journal of Civil Engineering* **18**(2), 639–645 (2014)
- [65] Fellendorf, M., Vortisch, P.: Microscopic traffic flow simulator VISSIM. *Fundamentals of traffic simulation*, 63–93 (2010)
- [66] Papathanasopoulou, V., Antoniou, C.: Flexible car-following models on mixed traffic trajectory data. In: Proceedings of the 96th Annual Meeting of the Transportation Research Board (2017)
- [67] Siddharth, S., G., R.: Calibration of VISSIM for indian heterogeneous traffic conditions. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* **104**, 380–389 (2013)
- [68] Rasouli, S., Timmermans, H.: Activity-based models of travel demand promises, progress and prospects. *Int. J. Urban Sci.* **18**(1), 31–60 (2014)

- [69] Ziemke, D., Nagel, K., Bhat, C.: Integrating CEMDAP and MATSim to increase the transferability of transport demand models. *Transp. Res. Rec. J. Transp. Res. Board* **2493**, 117–125 (2015)
- [70] Castiglione, J., Grady, B., Bowman, J., Bradley, M., Lawe, S.: Building an integrated activity-based and dynamic network assignment model. In: *Proceedings of the 3rd Transportation Research Board Conference on Innovations in Travel Modeling* (2010)
- [71] Roughgarden, T.: On the severity of braess’s paradox: Designing networks for selfish users is hard. *Journal of Computer and System Sciences* **72**(5), 922–953 (2006). Special Issue on FOCS 2001
- [72] Messaoudi, O., Lahlouhi, A.: An agent-based intervehicle cooperative robust car-following model for longitudinal control under uncertainty. *Int. J. Computer Applications in Technology* **58**(2), 150–164 (2018)
- [73] Wiedemann, R.: *Simulation des strassenverkehrsflusses*. Band 8, Schriftenreihe des Instituts für Verkehrswesen der Universität Karlsruhe, Karlsruhe, Germany (1974)
- [74] Gipps, P.G.: A behavioural car-following model for computer simulation. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological* **15**(2), 105–111 (1981) [https://doi.org/10.1016/0191-2615\(81\)90037-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0191-2615(81)90037-0)
- [75] Kraus, S.: *Microscopic Modeling of Traffic Flow: Investigation of Collision Free Vehicle Dynamics*
- [76] Treiterer, J.: *Investigation of Traffic Dynamics by Aerial Photogrammetric Techniques*
- [77] Wu, F., Stern, R., Churchill, M., Work, D.: Measuring trajectories and fuel consumption in oscillatory traffic: Experimental results. In: *Proc. 96 Th Annu. Meeting Transp. Res. Board*, pp. 1–14 (2017)
- [78] Asaithambi, G., Kanagaraaj, V., Srinivasan, K., Sivanandan, R.: Study of traffic flow characteristics using different vehicle-following models under mixed traffic conditions. *Transp. Lett.* **10**(2), 92–103 (2016) <https://doi.org/10.1080/19427867.2016.1190887>
- [79] Benzoni-Gavage, S., Colombo, R.M.: An n-populations model for traffic flow. *Eur. J. Appl. Math.* **14**(5), 587–612 (2003)
- [80] Clark, S.: Traffic prediction using multivariate nonparametric regression. *J. Transp. Eng.* **129**(2), 161–168 (2003)

- [81] Han, K., Sun, Y., Liu, H., Friesz, T.L., Yao, T.: A bi-level model of dynamic traffic signal control with continuum approximation. *Transp. Res. Part C, Emerg. Technol.* **55**, 409–431 (2015)
- [82] Chen, L.W., Chang, C.C.: Cooperative traffic control with green wave coordination for multiple intersections based on the internet of vehicles. *IEEE Trans. Syst. Man Cybern.: Syst.* **47**(7), 1321–1335 (2017)
- [83] White, R.H., Spengler, J.D., Dilwali, K.M., Barry, B.E., Samet, J.M.: Report of workshop on traffic, health, and infrastructure planning. *Arch. Environ. Occup. Health* **60**(2), 70–76 (2005)
- [84] Bhavathrathan, B., Mallikarjuna, C.: Evolution of macroscopic models for modeling the heterogeneous traffic: An indian perspective. *Transp. Lett.* **4**(1), 29–39 (2012)
- [85] Waizman, G., Shoval, S., Benenson, I.: Micro-simulation model for assessing the risk of vehicle–pedestrian road accidents. *J. Intell. Transp. Syst. Technol. Plan. Oper.* **19** (2014)
- [86] Gibson, J.J.: *The Ecological Approach to Visual Perception*, 1st edition edn. Psychology Press. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315740218>
- [87] Scarsini, M., Schröder, M., Tomala, T.: Dynamic atomic congestion games with seasonal flows. In: *HEC Paris Research Papers* (2013)
- [88] Braess, D.: Uber ein paradoxon aus der verkehrsplanung. *Unternehmensforschung* **12**, 258–268 (1968)
- [89] Rossi, R., Gastaldi, M., Meneguzzer, C., Gecchele, G.: Gap-acceptance behavior at a priority intersection: field observations versus experiments of a driving simulator. In: *Proceedings of the 90th Transportation Research Board Meeting* (2011)
- [90] Kim, H., Miranda Anon, A., Misu, T., Li, N., Tawari, A., Fujimura, K.: Look at me: Augmented reality pedestrian warning system using an in-vehicle volumetric head up display. In: *Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces*, pp. 294–298. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2856767.2856815>
- [91] Grácio, B.J.C., Wentink, M., Valente Pais, A.R.: Driver behavior comparison between static and dynamic simulation for advanced driving maneuvers. *Presence Teleop. Virt. Environ.* **20**(2), 143–161 (2011) https://doi.org/10.1162/pres_a.00040
- [92] Saifuzzaman, M., Zheng, Z.: Incorporating human factors in car-following models: a review of recent developments and research needs. *Transportation research*

part C: emerging technologies **48**, 379–403 (2014)

- [93] Fitzpatrick, K., Elefteriadou, L., Harwood, D.W., Collins, J.M., McFadden, J., Anderson, I.B., Krammes, R.A., Irizarry, N., Parma, K.D., Bauer, K.M., Passetti, K.: Speed Prediction for Two-Lane Rural Highways
- [94] Pérez, A.M., García, A., Torregrosa, F.J., D’Attoma, P.: Modeling operating speed and deceleration on two-lane rural roads with global positioning system data. *Transportation Research Record* (2171), 11–20 (2010)
- [95] Hu, W., Donnell, E.T.: Models of acceleration and deceleration rates on a complex two lane rural highway: results from a nighttime driving experiment. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour* **13**(6), 397–406 (2010)
- [96] Bennett, C.R.: A Speed Prediction Model for Rural Two-lane Highways
- [97] Connelly, M.L., Conaglen, H.M., Parsonson, B.S., Isler, R.B.: Child pedestrian’s crossing gap thresholds. *Accid. Anal. Prev* **30**, 443–453 (1998)
- [98] Hoffman, E.R., Payne, A., Prescott, S.: Children’s estimates of vehicle approach times. *Hum. Factors* **22**, 235–240 (1980)
- [99] McKelvey, R.K.: Can children learn to discriminate safe road-crossing intervals? *J. Safety Res.* **15**, 57–67 (1984)
- [100] Oxley, J., Fildes, B.N., Ihsen, E., Charlton, J.L., Day, R.H.: Crossing roads safely: an experimental study of age differences in gap selection by pedestrians. *Accid. Anal. Prev.* **27**, 962–971 (2005)
- [101] Plumert, J.M., Kearney, J.K., Cremer, J.F.: Children’s perception of gap affordances: bicycling across traffic-filled intersections in an immersive virtual environment. *Child Dev.* **75**, 1243–1253 (2004)
- [102] Simpson, G., Johnston, L., Richardson, M.: An investigation of road crossing in a virtual environment. *Accid. Anal. Prev.* **35**, 787–796 (2003)
- [103] Drew, D.R.: *Traffic Flow Theory and Control*. McGraw-Hill, ??? (1968)
- [104] Arasan, V.T., Arkatkar, S.S.: Microsimulation study of effect of volume and road width on PCU of vehicles under heterogeneous traffic. *Journal of Transportation Engineering* **136**(12), 1110–1119 (2010) [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)TE.1943-5436.0000176](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)TE.1943-5436.0000176)
- [105] Tanner, J.C.: A theoretical analysis of delays at an uncontrolled intersection. *Biometrika* **49**(1/2), 163 (1962)
- [106] Smeed, R.J.: Road capacity of city centers. *Traffic Engineering and Control* **8**(7)

(1966)

- [107] Chaudhry, M.S., Ranjitkar, P.: Capacity analysis of signalised intersection using microsimulation. In: Proceedings of the 32nd Australasian Transport Research Forum (ATRF), Auckland, Australia (2009)
- [108] Elefteriadou, L.: An Introduction to Traffic Flow Theory. Springer, ??? (2011)
- [109] Rodegerdts, L.A., Malinge, A., Marnell, P.S., al.: Accelerating Roundabouts in the United States
- [110] Transportation Research Board: Highway Capacity Manual (HCM) 2010
- [111] Dahl, J., Lee, C.: Empirical estimation of capacity for roundabouts using adjusted gap acceptance parameters for trucks. *Transp. Res. Rec.* (2312), 34–45 (2012)
- [112] Al-Madani, H.M.N.: Dynamic vehicular delay comparison between a police-controlled roundabout and a traffic signal. *Transp. Res. Part A: Policy Prac.* **37**(8), 681–688 (2003)
- [113] Easa, S.M., Mehmood, A.: Optimizing geometric design of roundabouts: multi-objective analysis. *Can. J. Civil Eng.* **33**(1), 29–40 (2006)
- [114] Ma, W., al.: Integrated optimization of lane markings and timings for signalized roundabouts. *Transp. Res. Part C: Emer.* **36**, 307–323 (2013)
- [115] Vasconcelos, A., Seco, A., Silva, A.: Comparison of procedures to estimate critical headways at roundabouts. *Promet* **25**(1), 43–53 (2013)
- [116] Mauro, R., Cattani, M.: Functional and economic evaluations for choosing road intersection layout. *Promet* **24**(5), 441–448 (2012)
- [117] Mandavilli, S., McCartt, A.T., Retting, R.A.: Crash patterns and potential engineering countermeasures at maryland roundabouts. *Traffic Inj. Prev.* **10**(1), 44–50 (2009)
- [118] Kim, S., Choi, J.: Safety analysis of roundabout designs based on geometric and speed characteristics. *KSCE J. Civil Eng.* **17**, 1446–1454 (2013)
- [119] Soren, U.: Safety effects of converting intersections to roundabouts. *Trans. Res. Rec.* **2389**, 22–29 (2013)
- [120] Mauro, R.: Calculation of Roundabouts - Capacity, Waiting Phenomena and Reliability. Springer, ??? (2010)
- [121] Montella, A., al.: International overview of roundabout design practices and insights for improvement of the italian standard. *Can. J. Civil Eng.* **40**(12),

1215–1226 (2013)

- [122] Yap, Y.H., Gibson, H.M., Waterson, B.J.: An international review of roundabout capacity modelling. *Transp. Rev.* **33**(5), 593–616 (2013)
- [123] Surdonja, S., Deluka-Tibljias, A., Babic, S.: Optimization of roundabout design elements. *Tehnicki vjesnik-Technical Gazette* **20**(3), 533–539 (2013)
- [124] Pilko, H., Brcic, D., Subic, N.: Study of vehicle speed in the design of roundabouts. *GRADEVINAR* **66**(5), 407–416 (2014)
- [125] Kumar, G., James, A.T., Choudhary, K., Sahai, R., Song, W.K.: Investigation and analysis of implementation challenges for autonomous vehicles in developing countries using hybrid structural modeling. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* **185**, 122080 (2022) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.122080>
- [126] Masello, L., Sheehan, B., Castignani, G., Shannon, D., Murphy, F.: On the impact of advanced driver assistance systems on driving distraction and risky behaviour: An empirical analysis of irish commercial drivers. *Accident Analysis & Prevention* **183**, 106969 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2023.106969>
- [127] Lombard, A., Noubli, A., Abbas-Turki, A., Gaud, N., Galland, S.: Deep reinforcement learning approach for V2X managed intersections of connected vehicles. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* **24**(7), 7178–7189 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1109/TITS.2023.3253867>
- [128] Cidjeu Djeuthie, D., Wakponou Addie Bernice, N., Tchappi, I., Mualla, Y., Najjar, A., Galland, S.: Intelligent transportation systems in developing countries: Challenges and prospects. In: 20th International Conference on Mobile Systems and Pervasive Computing (MobiSPC-23). Elsevier, Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2023.09.030> . <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877050923010773>
- [129] Zhang, H., Jin, X., Wang, L., al.: Multi-agent based modeling of spatiotemporal dynamical urban growth in developing countries: simulating future scenarios of lianyungang city, china. *Stoch. Environ. Res. Risk Assess.* **29**, 63–78 (2015) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00477-014-0942-z>
- [130] Dia, H.: An agent-based approach to modelling driver route choice behaviour under the influence of real-time information. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies* **10**(5/6), 331–349 (2002) [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0968-090X\(02\)00025-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0968-090X(02)00025-6)
- [131] Bouhsissin, S., Sael, N., Benabbou, F.: Driver behavior classification: A systematic literature review. *IEEE Access* **PP** (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3243865>

- [132] Zaidan, R.A., Alamoodi, A.H., Zaidan, B.B., Zaidan, A.A., Albahri, O.S., Talal, M., Garfan, S., Sulaiman, S., Mohammed, A., Kareem, Z.H., Malik, R.Q., Ameen, H.A.: Comprehensive driver behaviour review: Taxonomy, issues and challenges, motivations and research direction towards achieving a smart transportation environment. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence* **111**, 104745 (2022) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2022.104745>
- [133] Elamrani Abou El Assad, Z., Mousannif, H., Al Moatassime, H., Karkouch, A.: The application of machine learning techniques for driving behavior analysis: A conceptual framework and a systematic literature review. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence* **87**, 103312 (2020) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2019.103312>
- [134] Saleh, Y., Mahat, H., Hashim, M., Nayan, N., Suhaily, S., Khairul Anuar Ghazali, M., Hayati, R., Kurnia Sri Utami, R.: A systematic literature review (slr) on the development of sustainable heritage cities in malaysia. *Journal of Regional and City Planning* **32**(3) (2021) <https://doi.org/10.5614/jpwk.2021.32.3.6>
- [135] Tchappi, I., Galland, S., Kamla, V.C., Kamgang, J.-C., Mualla, Y., Najjar, A., Hilaire, V.: A critical review of holonic technology in traffic and transportation fields. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence* **1-54**(90), 1–54 (2020) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2020.103503>
- [136] Mualla, Y., Najjar, A., Daoud, A., Galland, S., Nicolle, C., Yasar, A.-U.-H., Shakshuki, E.: Agent-based simulation of unmanned aerial vehicles in civilian applications: A systematic literature review and research directions. *Future Generation Computer Systems* **100**, 344–364 (2019) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2019.04.051>
- [137] Mkhinini, M.M., Narsis Labbani, O., Nicolle, C.: Combining UML and ontology: An exploratory survey. *Computer Science Review* **35**(100223) (2020) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosrev.2019.100223>
- [138] Calvaresi, D., Eggenschwiler, S., Mualla, Y., Schumacher, M.I., Calbimonte, J.-P.: Exploring agent-based chatbots: a systematic literature review. *Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing* (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12652-023-04626-5>